

MES-CoBraD

Multidisciplinary Expert System
for the Assessment & Management
of Complex Brain Disorders

D7.1

System requirements & architecture

January 2022

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www.mes-cobrad.eu

PREFACE

The Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders (MES-CoBraD) is an interdisciplinary project combining Real-World Data (RWD) from multiple clinical and consumer sources through comprehensive, cost-efficient, and fast protocols towards improving diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic outcomes in people with Complex Brain Disorders (CoBraD), as reflected in Neurocognitive (Dementia), Sleep, and Seizure (Epilepsy) disorders and their interdependence.

- 1 It brings together internationally recognised experts in medicine, engineering, computer science, social health science, law, and marketing and communication from across Europe, and combines clinical information and scientific research in CoBraD with technical innovation in secure data-sharing platforms, artificial intelligence algorithms, and expert systems of precision and personalised care, with a primary focus on improving the quality of life of patients, their caregivers, and the society at large.
- 2 It leverages RWD from diverse CoBraD populations across cultural, socioeconomic, educational, and health system backgrounds, with special attention on including vulnerable populations and minorities in an equitable manner and engaging key stakeholders to maximise project impact.
- 3 The project will deliver a rigorous and self-standing methodology that will drive the MES-CoBraD implementation and define its operational principles; The MES-CoBraD solution, through the implementation of novel, self-standing AI based components and their integration under a common platform for scientific exploitation will assist focusing on the evaluation and validation of the solution, the spread of the excellence gained, the expansion of its ecosystem and the real-life sustainability.

CONSORTIUM

NTUA	National Technical University of Athens	EL
NIA	Neurological Institute of Athens	EL
HSCSP	Fundació privada Institut de Recerca de l'Hospital de la Santa Creu i Sant Pau	IR
VUB - LSTS	VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL	BE
UU	UPPSALA UNIVERSITY	SE
CHS-RMC	Clalit Health Services- Rabin Medical Center Cognitive Neurology and Epilepsy Clinics	IL
KCL	King's College London	UK
HOLISTIC	HOLISTIC P.C.	EL
SIMAVI	Software Imagination & Vision	RO
LIBER	STICHTING LIBER	NL
ENG	Engineering - Ingegneria Informatica S.p.A.	EN
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UE	University of Edinburgh	UK
CEL	CyberEthics Lab	IT

MULTIDISCIPLINARY EXPERT SYSTEM FOR THE ASSESSMENT & MANAGEMENT OF COMPLEX BRAIN DISORDERS

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation / Acronym	Description
API	Application Programming Interface
BPMN	Business Process Management (in some contexts it may mean Business Process Model Notation)
CIA	Confidentiality, integrity and availability
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CSV	Comma Separated Values
DB	Database
DME	Data Mashup Editor
DoA	Description of Action
Dx.y	Deliverable number y belonging to WP x
ERD	Entity Relationship Diagram
GUI	Graphical User Interface
H2020	Horizon 2020
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LDAP	Lightweight Directory Access Protocol
MES-CoBraD	Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders
MRI	Magnetic Resonance Imaging
Mx	Month x
PHP	PHP Hypertext Reprocessor
PUC	Pilot Use Case
RAM	Random Access Memory
REST	Representational State Transfer
SAML	Security Assertion Markup Language
SQL	Structured Query Language
TBD	To Be Decided
ToC	Table of Contents
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader
XML	Extensible Markup Language

Executive Summary

This deliverable (D7.1) presents the MES-CoBraD System requirements and Platform Architecture specification. Starting from the developed scenarios in the eHealth ecosystem, in this deliverable will be identified **technical requirements** and will be grouped into sets of **functional requirements** and **non-functional requirements**. It will be a description of how the identified requirements relate to each other and what their priority is. Next, the requirements will be mapped to components developed by the technology providers and will be characterised in terms of technological maturity, available technical solutions, and implementation risks.

Finally, the proposed components are placed in the whole architecture of the system, which will conclude the deliverable.

The deliverable starts with the presentation of the methodological approach. Next a catalogue of components is inserted. A comprehensive chapter with the user requirements, gathered in several rounds of analysis, is the next part of the document. It contains the user roles and functional requirements, for each component mentioned in the catalogue.

The proposed implementation, designed to cover the requirements is presented in the next two chapters which describe the architecture.

First a high-level architecture is presented. It refers to several views:

- › Use case view
- › Logical View
- › Development View
- › Information View
- › Deployment view
- › Security view
- › Integration view

The detailed architecture is presenting the main layers of the system which are:

- › **Component Layer**, covering the components of the platform. The layer includes the cloud components, common infrastructure and specific components.
- › **Communication Layer**, covering the link from the external world into the platform. The layer includes tools for data sharing, synchronous and asynchronous communication.
- › **Information Layer**, covering the data used by the platform, i.e. Data collected, Data Lake, User Management.
- › **Function Layer**, covering the main groups of functions available in the system, including Data Preparation, Query Builder, Advanced Analytics, Data and Results Visualisation, Expert Systems, Artificial Intelligence, MRI quality control, Questionnaire Builder.
- › **Business Layer**, covering the business value of the system.

The document is created to be used in the next steps of system implementation as reference for analysts, developers and testers.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 OBJECTIVES AND SCOPE OF WORK

1.1.1 PROJECT OBJECTIVES

The Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders (MES-CoBraD) is an interdisciplinary project, combining **Real-World Data (RWD)** from multiple clinical and consumer sources through comprehensive, cost-efficient, and fast protocols towards improving diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic outcomes in people with **Complex Brain Disorders (CoBraD), as reflected in Neurocognitive (Dementia), Sleep, and Seizure (Epilepsy) disorders and their interdependence.** It brings together internationally recognised experts in medicine, engineering, computer science, social health science, law, and marketing and communication from across Europe, and combines clinical information and scientific research in CoBraD with technical innovation in secure data-sharing platforms, artificial intelligence algorithms, and expert systems of precision and personalised care, with a primary focus on improving the quality of life of patients, their caregivers, and the society at large. It leverages RWD from diverse CoBraD populations across cultural, socioeconomic, educational, and health system backgrounds, with special attention on including vulnerable populations and minorities in an equitable manner and engaging key stakeholders to maximise project impact.

This task and deliverable lead and present the end-user requirements analysis for the entire MES-CoBraD project and the resulting multidisciplinary expert system for the assessment and management of complex brain disorders (MES-CoBraD). As such, the general objective of the project also defines the purpose and scope of the analysis carried out according to T7.1. The overall objective of the project is to develop a platform to correlate data collected from different data sources to improve diagnosis, accuracy, and therapeutic outcomes in people with complex brain disorders as well as reflection in neurocognitive disorders (dementia), sleep and seizure (Epilepsy) disorders and their interdependence.

In order to meet the objective of the project, the needs of end-users will be identified and requirements will be established covering the scientific, technological and societal aspects of the project throughout its duration, as well as the exploitation of the project results thereafter.

Scientific objectives are focused on scientific and research work that will provide results for a rigorous and autonomous methodology, which will lead to the implementation of MES-CoBraD and define its operational principles. Technical objectives focus on the delivery of the MES-CoBraD solution, by implementing new, autonomous, AI-based components that will be integrated into a common platform for scientific exploitation. Societal objectives are represented by the evaluation and validation of the solution, the spread of the acquired excellence, the extension of its ecosystem, and the sustainability in real life. (DoA, Part B, p.7).

1.1.2 WP7 OBJECTIVES

WP7 “Integrated Clinical Research Platform” will integrate the components developed in WP5 with the additional components of WP6 under a common interoperable fully functional infrastructure and ensure their effective communication. It will be the integration of the various developed components under a common clinical research platform.

The deliverables from WP7 will present all the stages of the platform development, starting from the technical requirements, the architecture, the integration of the components developed in WP5 & WP6, the testing phase and the release of the 2 versions of the platform. In the last version, all the components will be fully integrated, tested in the pilots and the feedback from the pilot deployment was taken into consideration.

1.1.3 D7.1 OBJECTIVES

Starting from the developed scenarios in the eHealth ecosystem, in this deliverable will be identified **technical requirements** and grouped into sets of **functional requirements** and **non-functional requirements**. It will be a description of how the identified requirements relate to each other and what is their priority. Finally, the requirements will be mapped to components developed by the technology providers and will be characterised in terms of technological maturity, available technical solutions, and implementation risks.

Also, the partners will derive and document **the conceptual architecture of the integrated MES CoBraD platform**.

The architecture will describe in detail the integration logic and interfaces between the involved tools and services produced by WP5 and WP6, as well as the interaction of the components and user interfaces. The architecture will comprise:

1. A definition of the initial reference model of the MES-CoBraD platform, which will identify the scope of the individual components and services and the context where they will operate.
2. The design of the components' functional architecture, which specifies the functions to be performed by the components, defines the interrelations between the functions and qualifies data sources and data flows.
3. The design of MES-CoBraD components' information and communication architectures, which establishes how data flows and data exchange are actuated.
4. The definition of a service-oriented architecture approach considering the interaction dynamics between components.

The Consortium will design the architecture of the integrated MES-CoBraD platform to facilitate interoperability and to allow for extensibility, while preserving a considerable degree of implementation-platform-independence.

1.2 RELATIONS TO OTHER WORK PACKAGES, TASKS AND DELIVERABLES

The deliverable "D7.1 – System requirements & architecture", including tasks T7.1 and T7.2, produces outputs that represent inputs for the other tasks in different work packages. On the other hand, there are WPs that represent inputs for deliverable D7.1. This relation is represented below:

- › D7.1 provides specifications, requirements and infrastructure for T5.1 in order to assure data integration and harmonisation for heterogeneous data sources;
- › D7.1 provides inputs for T5.2. This task is devoted to deal with the security and anonymisation requirements;
- › T5.3's objective will be to maximise and speed up the distribution and expansion of research results through the sharing of knowledge. This task aims to equip the data management layer with instruments capable to enable the co-design of algorithms of analysis, the sharing of data and their exploitation through "easy to use" resources. D7.1 provides requirements for implementation of this task;
- › D7.1 provides specifications, requirements, infrastructure design and preparation for T6.1 - Expert System (ES), that will be developed and validated, relies on artificial intelligence algorithms and will guide decision making. The ES will work as knowledge acquisition, model-

based reasoning and system integration that gives decision support on diagnosis, prognosis, and therapy;

- › T6.2 is implemented based on the specifications, requirements and infrastructure design provided by D7.1;
- › D7.1 provides inputs for T6.3. The MES-CoBraD Platform will implement an Artificial Intelligence (AI) knowledge-based system for data analysis and interpretation;
- › T7.3 will take input from the architectural framework developed in T7.1 and will integrate the software components developed in WP5 and WP6 to form a sound MES-CoBraD platform;
- › T7.4 targets the continuous validation, evaluation, and improvement of the Platform, based on specifications, requirements and infrastructure provided by D7.1;
- › WP2 provides information about legal, ethics and security frameworks, necessary for developing of D7.1;
- › WP3 - Landscape analysis & Methodology provides necessary information for entire project implementation and inputs for D7.1.

Figure 1: Relation to other Work Packages

1.3 INTENDED AUDIENCE

The level of dissemination of this document is “Public”. It is designed for the following types of audiences:

1. Members of the Consortium: particularly end users, project managers, analysts, developers and testers as well as any other personnel involved in the project.
2. Members of the of the European Commission services, particularly our project officer and monitors.
3. More technically minded members of the general public interested in the subject of this report

1.4 CHAPTER STRUCTURE

Following this introduction, in the next chapter, Chapter 2 *Methodological Approach*, we describe the methodological approach to both the process of elicitation and analysis of requirements, and system architecture design. We describe the main methodological elements as well as how they were implemented through the work carried out under Tasks 7.1 and 7.2.

In Chapter 3 *Catalogue of DoA Mentioned Components* we provide a short catalogue of the MES-CoBraD System Components that were mentioned in the DoA. This catalogue is the result of collecting information by means of a Technologies (Tools/Components) and Capabilities Template.

Chapter 4 *User & Technical Requirements* presents the main outputs of our requirements analysis process. The chapter describes 107 functional requirements as mapped per each component and 21 non-functional requirements.

The System architecture is presented in next three chapters in increasing levels of detail: 5 *High-Level Architecture*, 6 *Architectural view model*, 7 *Detailed Layered Architecture*.

The *Conclusions* of this report are drawn in Chapter 8.

2 METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH

This chapter gives an overview of the methodological approach to Deliverable D7.1. In addition, more detailed methodological explanations as pertaining to each of the activities carried out in T7.1 & T7.2 resulting in D7.1, are provided in the chapters below.

2.1 A HYBRID APPROACH BETWEEN WATERFALL AND AGILE

Our project implementation follows a hybrid methodology between Waterfall and Agile. On the one hand, some waterfall features are required by the DoA and the overall structure of Horizon 2020 projects. For example, the grouping of activities in Tasks and Work Packages, broadly succeeding each other is specific to waterfall methodologies. Ample activities of requirements elicitation and architecture design at the beginning of the project are also specific to waterfall: with a long cycle of requirements/design -> development -> testing.

However, the project has also built-in features that are closer to Agile. While a long cycle of analysis/development/testing is followed, within this framework some flexibility is built in and necessary. While we frontloaded much of the process of analysis, D7.1 is only a first iteration of the requirements elicitation and architecture design process which should be sufficient to jumpstart and give direction to the technical implementation of the project. However, further iterations of requirements analysis will probably be needed. Detailed analysis may accompany the process of development and integration (under WPs 5, 6 & 7), which are expected to take place in shorter cycles/sprints. Specifically, Task 7.1 will continue throughout the project to support development and testing, while the system architecture may also evolve as the process of integration progresses.

Therefore, while we attempted to make this document as complete and “final” as possible, we expect it to be a live document that will evolve throughout the project. We shall document and explain changes made to the original (usually in further deliverables documenting development and integration).

2.2 AN ADAPTED STATE-OF-THE-ART GENERAL APPROACH

We are broadly following a state-of-the-art sequence of eliciting requirements and designing the solution architecture, as seen Figure 2.

Figure 2: Requirements Elicitation and Architecture Design Stages

Business Requirements are “statements of goals, objectives, and outcomes that describe why a change has been initiated. They can apply to the whole of an enterprise, a business area, or a specific initiative” (International Institute of Business Analysis, 2015, p. 16). The overall objectives of this Project have been defined, agreed among partners and presented to the European Commission in the DoA. We therefore consider this stage of requirements description as having been covered in the project writing phase. This document, in a sense is a continuation of the DoA in this respect. Moreover, some more detailed stipulations of the DoA were used as source for more detailed user and technical requirements (as explained below in Section 2.4.1).

User Requirements (sometimes also termed stakeholder requirements) are understood as “tasks or goals the users must be able to perform with the product that will provide value to someone. [...] User

requirements describe what the user will be able to do with the system.” (Wiegiers and Beatty, 2013, p. 9). Usually, these requirements are formulated at a broader level of generality than technical requirements. However, there are situations where already at the level of user requirements technical detail is provided, especially when prospective users have a good technical understanding.

Technical Requirements (sometimes also termed solution requirements) “describe the capabilities and qualities of a solution that meets the stakeholder [user] requirements. They provide appropriate level of detail to allow for the development and implementation of the solution” (International Institute of Business Analysis, 2015, p. 16) These requirements are usually split into two:

Functional Requirements “describe the capabilities that a solution must have in terms of the behaviour and information that the solution will manage” and

Non-Functional Requirements “do not relate directly to the behaviour of functionality of the solution, but rather describe conditions under which a solution must remain effective or qualities that a solution must have.” (International Institute of Business Analysis, 2015, p. 16)

In this document we merged the phases of eliciting user requirements and detailing technical requirements into one phase. This was justified by several factors:

1. Task 7.1 description in the DoA Requests us to go straight to formulating Technical Requirements.
2. Our End User Partners are highly technically savvy with deep understanding especially of statistical and data analysis but also IT issues. By the first formulation of their requirements, they had quite a bit of technical detail.
3. Our highly cooperative approach (see Section 2.3 below) allowed us to involve both technological and scientific partners (as well as others) in all phases of requirements formulation and architectural design.

Finally, the last phase presented in Figure 2 is *Architecture Design*. “The software architecture of a program or a computing system is the structure or structures of the system, which comprise software elements, the externally visible properties of those elements, and the relationships among them” (Bass et al., 2003, p. 3). While often requirements are presented in a separate document than the architecture (and indeed under the MES-CoBraD Project the two are Architecture design is the subject of Task 7.2, but this deliverable presents both the outputs of Tasks 7.1 and 7.2.

2.3 A CO-DESIGN INSPIRED APPROACH

To define user requirements, we follow an approach inspired by *cooperative design* (or in short co-design), which we think is appropriate for a project implemented in a wide consortium of 14 partners. *Co-design* (also termed in different contexts *participatory design*, *cooperative design*, or *co-creation*) refers to designing products, technological systems, etc. with an active participation and collaboration of various types of relevant actors (or stakeholders) such as designers, developers, customers, users, etc (Steen et al., 2011). A particular stakeholder group emphasised in co-design is the involvement of users, not just in passive capacity of rubberstamping system specifications, but as active actors and “competent practitioners” who have important knowledge to share in the design process (Carroll, 2004; Greenbaum and Kyng, 1991).

Applied to the MES-CoBraD Project, and Tasks T7.1 and T7.2, co-design means a concern for the active involvement of the various stakeholders (primarily, to begin with, internal stakeholders, i.e. Consortium Members and their personnel, but possibly expanding on this circle as the project progresses) in their various capacities and roles. The major classification of internal stakeholders by their role and type of implication in relation to the MES-CoBraD System (Note: this is different from the “project role” in terms

of partner's leadership or contributor position as related to Tasks, Work Packages or the entire Project):

Figure 3: Co-Design by Various Stakeholder Types

- › Scientific Partners/End User Partners: the partners/member of consortium who will be involved in using/piloting the MES-CoBraD System as end users/practitioners in the area of complex brain disorders. They contribute to the project with their business/scientific expertise in the area of complex brain disorders; they are a main actor in defining and validating user requirements as well as in piloting the System. Six (6) such organisations are present in the Project, to see specifically who they are see Table 1: , last column.¹
- › Technology Provider Partners: are members of the consortium who are in charge of providing technological solutions (either as responsible for components development or as integrators). Four (4) such organisations are present in the Project, to see specifically who they are see Table 1: , last column.
- › Other Expertise/Service Provider Partners – partners who are in neither category above, but have distinct role providing other expertise and/or services within the Project. Four (4) such organisations are present in the Project, to see specifically who they are see Table 1, last column.

¹ End User Organizations are not to be confused with end users at the individual level. At individual level end user roles are defined and identified in Section 4.2.

Table 1: Internal stakeholders/consortium members' overview

Name	Abbreviation	Country	Type	Partner role
NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS - NTUA	NTUA	Greece	Research	Technical
NEVROLOGIKO INSTITOUTO ATHINON-NIA-IDIOTIKO IATREIOIATRIKI MONOPROSWPI ETAIREIA PERIORISMENIS EFTHINIS	NIA	Greece	Healthcare: Clinical, Research, Education	Scientific
FUNDACIO PRIVADA INSTITUT DE RECERCA DE L'HOSPITAL DE LA SANTA CREU I SANT PAU	IR-HSCSP	Spain	Research	Scientific
VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL	VUB	Belgium	UNI	Other
UPPSALA UNIVERSITET	UU	Sweden	Clinical and research	Scientific
CLALIT HEALTH SERVICES	CHS-RMC	Israel		Scientific
KING'S COLLEGE LONDON	KCL	United Kingdom	Education and Research	Scientific
HOLISTIC IKE	HOLISTIC	Greece	Consultancy firm	Other
SOFTWARE IMAGINATION & VISION SRL	SIMAVI	Romania	Large Industry	Technical
STICHTING LIBER	LIBER	Netherlands	Non-profit / Association	Other
ENGINEERING - INGEGNERIA INFORMATICA SPA	ENG	Italy	Large Enterprise	Technical
MICHOPOULOS I. & CH. G.P.	EVOLUTION	Greece	Private commercial	Technical
THE UNIVERSITY OF EDINBURGH	UEDIN	United Kingdom	Education	Scientific
CYBERETHICS LAB SRLS	CEL	Italy	SME	Other

2.4 TASK INPUTS, ACTIVITIES AND OUTPUTS

To arrive at a first formalisation of solution requirements and the architectural design of the MES-CoBraD System, a variety of information sources, instruments and activities were used. Figure 4 provides an overview of such information sources (inputs and instruments), activities and outputs.

Figure 4 Tasks 7.1 & 7.2; Inputs, Instruments, Activities and Outputs

We describe below each of the instruments used and activities carried out.

2.4.1 DoA ANALYSIS

A careful analysis of the Description of Action (DoA) document (parts A and B) was carried out to define the scope and objectives of T7.1, T7.2 and D7.1, and ensure consistency with DoA and to make use of work that had been carried out during Project definition.

Moreover, the DoA was thus one of the sources in identifying user requirements. Our analysts carefully read the DoA Parts A and B, to identify any stipulations as to what the MES-CoBraD System and its components should do. 41 initial proposed requirements were identified from this source.

2.4.2 TECHNOLOGIES AND CAPABILITIES TEMPLATE

Many of the activities described below were focused on end users' organisations. However, to make use of information about Technologies/Components of the MES-CoBraD System and their capabilities we created a template to request this information from Technology Provider Partners.

The objective of the Technologies and Capabilities Template is to provide high and medium level descriptions of technologies (and their capabilities) available on the MES-CoBraD Project. This information was used for the following purposes:

1. To provide the overall project with an updated and more detailed description of the MES-CoBraD System Components, particularly the components stipulated in the DoA;
2. To inform the user requirements: the Technologies and Capabilities Template represented one major source based on which user requirements were generated.
3. To support the later definition of system specifications and architectural design of the MES-CoBraD Platform.

The template contains three pages.

1. The first provides an introduction and instructions to completing the template.
2. The second requires from technological partners a high-level description of MES-CoBraD technologies / components, and
3. The third page asks for a description of the functionalities/capabilities of the technology (existing or proposed to be developed in this project).

The template was developed by SIMAVI and proposed for discussion to the technical partners in the meetings held on WP7. It was then sent for consultation to the technical partners, and the final form of the template was sent to the technical partners to complete for each technology.

It should be noted that the given the fact that the template was applied in the beginning phases of T7.1, the components described using it are broadly the ones that are described in the DoA. Later, as system requirements were developed and progress toward architectural design made, more components were added. These were not described using this template, but requirements corresponding to them were described in Chapter 4.

The answers to the templates can be found in Chapter 3.

The following tables display the 3 pages of the Template. It should be noted however that the original document is an Excel document (available to project officer and monitors upon request). The Excel file included some additional information such as detailed definitions or instructions as to how to fill each cell (which appear once the user selects that cell as active), and for some answers predefined list of

answers were proposed. This information is lost when transposing the Excel template into Word.

Table 2: Technology and Capabilities Template – Page 1 – General Introduction and Instructions

<p>MES-CoBraD Project</p>	<p>MES-CoBraD Multidisciplinary Expert System for the Assessment & Management of Complex Brain Disorders</p>
<p>General Introduction and Instructions</p>	
<p>Objective:</p>	<p>The objective of this Template/Questionnaire is to provide high and medium level descriptions of Technologies (and their capabilities) available on the MES-CoBraD Project. This information will be used to inform the user requirements, system specifications, use cases and architectural design of the MES-CoBraD Platform.</p>
<p>Who should fill this template?</p>	<p>We are asking technological partners (i.e. partners in charge of various components of the MES-CoBraD System) to fill this template once per each technology they make available (e.g. if you have/are responsible for 3 technologies/components fill in the template once for each, in total 3 times).</p>
<p>Structure of Template</p>	<p>This template contains two tables (on the next two sheets). The first gives a high level description of Technologies/Components in MES-CoBraD, the later describes functionalities of the Technology (existing or proposed to be developed within this Project)</p>
<p>Final remarks</p>	<p>Detailed instructions for filling in each field can be seen by clicking on that field (provided you have a recent version of Excel).</p>
	<p>For any questions regarding this template please contact [<i>email addresses of analyst team were deleted in this document for privacy concerns</i>]</p>
	<p>Please send answers by replying to the email where this template was sent to you or by sending the completed template to [<i>email addresses of analyst team were deleted in this document for privacy concerns</i>]</p>

Table 3: Technology and Capabilities Template – Page 2 – Technology/Tool Description

Please read the Instructions Sheet prior to filling in this Table!	
Responsible Partner Abbreviated Name (per DoA)	
Technology/Component Name within MES-CoBraD	
Technology/Component Other Internal Name	
Corresponding Task in MES-CoBraD	
Is the technology developed/owned by Responsible Partner or third party?	
Current Technology Readiness Level (TRL)	
Planned Technology Readiness (TRL) by the end of MES-CoBraD	
Technology/Component History	
Technology/Component in the Present: Description	
Technology/Component at the End of Project: Description	
Technology at the End Of Project: Benefits	
Hardware/Networking (Low Level) Interfaces	
Software Interfaces (protocols, file types, standards)	
Other Information, Observations, etc.	

2.4.3 REQUIREMENTS WORKSHOPS AND WORK MEETINGS

Due to travel restrictions and pandemic risks all meetings under the MES-CoBraD Project were held online usually utilising in Microsoft Teams or Zoom.

To discuss and clarify system requirements a series of 4 dedicated workshops were held. We call them workshops (as distinct from other work meetings) since they had a narrower focus (discuss and clarify requirements), they were irregular (took place in a short window of time at times agreed ad hoc) and had longer duration. These workshops took place after some initial requirements were proposed by the End User / Scientific Partners, identified based on the DoA or proposed by Technological Partners via the Technologies and Capabilities Templates.

Table 5: User Requirements Workshops

Date	Time (CET)	Participants	Observations / Description
14.10.2021	13:00 - 15:30	EVOL, NTUA, SIMAVI, NIA, CEL, LIBER, KCL, HOLISTIC, ENG, VUB	6 of an initial list of 11 user proposed requirements were discussed and split into further 10 requirements. Being the first workshop, this tended to be less focused than the following discussions, nevertheless it was a useful and engaging discussion. A full recording of this workshop can be made available to the project officer and monitors upon request.
20.11.2021	14:40 - 15:20	EVOL, NTUA, ENG, SIMAVI, NIA, VUB-LSTS, CHS-RMC, IR-HSCSP, HOLISTIC, UPS, KCL, LIBER, UoE, CEL.	This meeting and presentation took place under MES-CoBraD 1 st Project Meeting. A presentation of WP7 status and approach to D7.1 was delivered in preparation of a longer discussion in the 2 nd day of the Meeting.
21.11.2021	10:00 - 18:00	EVOL, NTUA, ENG, SIMAVI, NIA, VUB-LSTS, CHS-RMC, IR-HSCSP, HOLISTIC, UPS, KCL, LIBER, UoE, CEL.	Most of the 2 nd day of the MES-CoBrad 1 st Project Meeting was dedicated to discussing user and technical requirements. Part of the meeting was split into several groups between technical partners and scientific partners, and then the groups were re-joined. A full recording of this workshop can be made available to the project officer and monitors upon request
29.10.2021	14:00 - 17:00	EVOL, NTUA, ENG, SIMAVI	A full recording of this workshop can be made available to the project officer and monitors upon request

In addition to dedicated requirements workshops, regular (usually weekly) WP7 meetings were held. Initially these meetings were focused mostly on discussing requirements, then gradually their focus shifted toward discussing the solution architecture.

Table 6: List of Work Package 7 Meetings

Date	Time (CET)	Participants	Observations / Description
08.10.2021	12:00 – 13:00	EVOL, NTUA, SIMAVI, NIA, ENG	Meeting minutes available to project officer and monitors upon request.
05.11.2021	13:00 – 14:30	EVOL, NTUA, ENG, SIMAVI, UU, NIA, LIBER	
12.11.2021	13:00 – 14:30	EVOL, NTUA, ENG, SIMAVI, NIA, HOLISTIC	
19.11.2021	13:00 – 14:30	EVOL, NTUA, SIMAVI	
26.11.2021	13:00 – 14:30	EVOL, NTUA, SIMAVI, NIA, UU, KCL	
03.12.2021	13:00 – 14:30	EVOL, NTUA, SIMAVI, CEL, ENG, HOLISTIC	
10.12.2021	13:00 – 14:30	EVOL, NTUA, SIMAVI, ENG, NIA, UU, KCL	
17.12.2021	13:00 – 14:30	NTUA, SIMAVI, ENG, UU	
14.01.2022	13:00 – 14:00	NTUA, SIMAVI, ENG, EVOL	
21.01.2022	13:00 – 13:40	NTUA, SIMAVI, ENG, EVOL, KLC, HOLISTIC	
28.01.2022	13:00 – 14:00	SIMAVI, ENG, NTUA, EVOL	

2.4.4 ONLINE DOCUMENT COLLABORATION

Aside from collaboration by completing information in templates and participation in meetings, central to our work process was online collaboration on working documents. For our project work we use a Microsoft SharePoint platform made available by NTUA at: <https://epuntuagr.sharepoint.com/sites/MES-CoBraD-Consortium/SitePages/>. All partners, and their personnel participating in the MES-CoBraD Project, were given credentials for accessing the platform and have the rights to view and edit documents.

One of the main working documents was an Excel file with the list of requirements. All partners were invited to review the requirements as the list evolved and to propose changes. Usually changes or issues were highlighted and then discussed at the next meetings before they were adopted. Multiple iterations of such marking of issues followed by discussion and changes to requirements were carried out.

Collaborative work was further carried out in the deliverable itself. Where partners were able to contribute or monitor progress and provide feedback.

Other documents such as diagram files for the system architecture were also shared on SharePoint.

2.5 ARCHITECTURE SPECIFIC METHODOLOGY (4+x)

Starting from a hybrid project concept that situates MES-CoBraD at the confluence of IT and business sector targeted, the tools developed during the project are based on the improvement of commercial tools and the integration of best-of-breed technologies. Although the selected technologies are currently available, the project envisions ground-breaking combination that will go beyond the state of the art as the technologies represent already leading-edge developments in their fields and will be combined for the first time in the MES-CoBraD domain.

Domain standardisation bodies ISO and CEN-CENELEC-ETSI provide architectural models for IT. Philippe Kruchten (Kruchten, 1995) introduced the “4+1” View Model for software architecture standardised as ISO/IEC/IEEE/42010 (IEC, 2011).

For the purpose of the current project, we are mapping the architectural models on a business layered model composed of 5 layers:

1. **Component** layer comprises of physical devices, including the equipment used to collect data and all Edge processing plug-ins responsible with the data anonymisation.
2. **Communication** layer describes protocols and mechanisms for information exchange.
3. **Information** layer shows data exchanged, data type, type of data collected, and data structure.
4. **Function** layer refers to information and data models from an architectural viewpoint.
5. **Business** layer describes business view on the information exchange and regulatory aspects related to MES-CoBraD data processing.

The international standard ISO/IEC/IEEE/42010 (IEC, 2011) provides various architectural model such as ‘4+1’ view model of architecture (Kruchten, 1995) which organises a description of the software architecture using five concurrent views aiming to address a specific set of concerns.

In the study referenced in (Kruchten, 1995), the data model has not been explicitly treated as an architectural view. Indeed, the information provided by a data model is considered included and reported by the logical view. On the contrary, Merson (2009) suggests the use of the data model as an architectural approach aiming at supporting software architects in creating data model architectural views able to provide information about the data exchanged.

Initially, the 4+1 architectural model described logical, process, physical and development views accompanied by scenarios. Since then, a lot of variations starting from this model were described to accommodate needs and technological advancement. Some models propose a 4+x architecture comprising of functional, information, concurrency, development, deployment, and operational views. (Woods and Rozanski, 2005).

The “4+x” architecture model was adjusted to intertwine with the layered business model. An overview of each “4+x” architectural view, as proposed for MES-CoBraD (Figure 5), is detailed as follows:

- › **Use cases** view serves two main purposes: as a driver to discover the architectural elements during the architecture design as a validation and illustration role after this architecture design is complete.
- › **Function** view describes the functional elements of MES-CoBraD system, their responsibilities, interfaces, and interactions.
- › **Development** view focuses on software modules and subsystems in the development environment.
- › **Deployment** view describes the physical environment, where the system is intended to run.

- › **Information** view describes flows of information in parallel or sequential execution of internal tasks.
- › **Security** view describes security attributes.
- › **Integration** view describes how the overall system will be operated, administrated, and deployed in the value chain.

Figure 5. MES-CoBrad 4+x architectural views

To collect relevant details from MES-CoBraD technology providers a dedicated survey was designed and deployed. The tool information is gathered and cross-evaluated overall and per architectural views in Chapters 5, 6 & 7.

3 CATALOGUE OF DOA MENTIONED COMPONENTS

3.1 OVERVIEW OF MES-COBRA D COMPONENTS

This chapter provides a presentation of the Components mentioned in the DOA of the MES-CoBraD System as described in the Technologies and Capabilities Template. This represents thus an early view of the list of components and their descriptions. At the beginning of Tasks 7.1 & 7.2 a request and template were sent to technological partners (NTUA, ENG and EVOL) to describe the components/tool (and their capabilities/functionalities present or expected) which by DOA were in their lead responsibility. In this chapter we present the information collected by means of the Technologies/Tools and Capabilities template. Table 7 presents an overview of the components mentioned in the DOA for which the Technologies and Capabilities Template was completed. The following subsections of this Chapter present each Component one by one. For each Component two tables are presented corresponding to pages 2 & 3 of the Technologies and Capabilities Template (as described in Section 2.4.2)

It should be noted that following the process of requirements analysis, the need for additional components/tools was identified and their requirements described. Therefore Chapters 4 and the following consider a more complete view of the components of the MES-CoBraD System. Moreover, some updates to the description of components were done and they are reflected in Chapter 7.

Table 7: MES-CoBraD Technologies/Components

Relevant Products/ Technology	TRL Current	TRL Target	Task	Responsible (cf. Part A)
Data Analytics	1	6	T6.2	NTUA
Data Visualiser	1	6	T6.2	NTUA
Query Builder	4	6	T6.2	NTUA
Data Lake	7	8	T5.1	ENG
Data Harmonisation Module	7	8	T5.1	ENG
Data Ingestion Module	7	8	T5.1	ENG
Expert System	1	9	T6.1	EVOL
Artificial Intelligence	1	9	T6.3	EVOL

3.2 DATA ANALYTICS - NTUA

Table 8: Data Analytics Description

Responsible Partner Abbreviated Name (per DoA)	NTUA
Technology/Component Name within MES-CoBraD	Data Analytics
Technology/Component Other Internal Name	
Corresponding Task in MES-CoBraD	T6.2
Is the technology developed/owned by Responsible Partner or third party?	NTUA
Current Technology Readiness Level (TRL)	TRL 1 – basic principles observed
Planned Technology Readiness (TRL) by the end of MES-CoBraD	TRL 6 – technology demonstrated in relevant environment
Technology/Component History	This component is in the phase of designing and collecting the requirements. This component will be developed using a Python Framework
Technology/Component in the Present: Description	This component is in the phase of designing and collecting the requirements. This component will be developed using a Python Framework
Technology/Component at the End of Project: Description	At the end of the project, this component will be able to analyse data (images, timeseries etc.) and implement hypothesis testing
Technology at the End Of Project: Benefits	A scientist or a clinician will be able to use this component to analyse data or run hypothesis testing.
Hardware/Networking (Low Level) Interfaces	-
Software Interfaces (protocols, file types, standards)	This component will be a back-end RESTful API service that will process data in JSON or csv format.
Other Information, Observations, etc.	-

Table 9: Data Analytics Capabilities

Capability / Functionality Title	Description	User roles	Current Maturity/ Readiness (TRL)	Target Maturity/ Readiness (TRL)	Proposed Priority Level	Interface (service, methods, data structures)
Data Analytics	This component will be used for the process and analysis of data, as well as for performing statistical analyses and hypothesis testing. It will include statistics packages, imaging and time-series analysis components	clinician/scientist	TRL 1 – basic principles observed	TRL 6 – technology demonstrated in relevant environment	Must Have	Not defined

3.3 DATA VISUALISER – NTUA

Table 10: Data Visualiser Description

Responsible Partner Abbreviated Name (per DoA)	NTUA
Technology/Component Name within MES-CoBraD	Data Visualiser
Technology/Component Other Internal Name	
Corresponding Task in MES-CoBraD	T6.2
Is the technology developed/owned by Responsible Partner or third party?	NTUA
Current Technology Readiness Level (TRL)	TRL 1 – basic principles observed
Planned Technology Readiness (TRL) by the end of MES-CoBraD	TRL 6 – technology demonstrated in relevant environment
Technology/Component History	This component is in the phase of designing and collecting the requirements.
Technology/Component in the Present: Description	This component is in the phase of designing and collecting the requirements.
Technology/Component at the End of Project: Description	This component will provide dashboards and visualisations over imaging data and timeseries for one or more patients.
Technology at the End Of Project: Benefits	A scientist or a clinical will be able to receive insightful visualisations.
Hardware/Networking (Low Level) Interfaces	-
Software Interfaces (protocols, file types, standards)	This component will receive data in JSON format, which will be depicted in charts and dashboards.
Other Information, Observations, etc.	-

Table 11: Data Visualiser Capabilities

Capability /Functionality Title	Description	User roles	Current Maturity/ Readiness (TRL)	Target Maturity/ Readiness (TRL)	Proposed Priority Level	Interface (service, methods, data structures)
Visualisation	It will visualise the data using a number of different charts, figures or a dashboard, as well as using external libraries for imaging and timeseries data	clinician/scientist	TRL 1 – basic principles observed	TRL 6 – technology demonstrated in relevant environment	Must Have	Not defined

3.4 QUERY BUILDER - NTUA

Table 12: Query Builder Description

Responsible Partner Abbreviated Name (per DoA)	NTUA
Technology/Component Name within MES-CoBraD	Query Builder
Technology/Component Other Internal Name	
Corresponding Task in MES-CoBraD	T6.2
Is the technology developed/owned by Responsible Partner or third party?	NTUA
Current Technology Readiness Level (TRL)	TRL 4 – technology validated in lab
Planned Technology Readiness (TRL) by the end of MES-CoBraD	TRL 6 – technology demonstrated in relevant environment
Technology/Component History	This component will be used to build SQL queries and will be based on services developed in past projects for other fields (e.g. the Big Data Ocean project)
Technology/Component in the Present: Description	The Query Builder currently available is able to build SQL queries receiving as input data in JSON format. It works only with tabular data.
Technology/Component at the End of Project: Description	The Query Builder will be able to build complex SQL queries receiving as input data in JSON format
Technology at the End Of Project: Benefits	Other components will be able to leverage the functionalities of Query Builder in order to receive data
Hardware/Networking (Low Level) Interfaces	-
Software Interfaces (protocols, file types, standards)	This component will be a back-end RESTful API service that will build SQL queries, execute this query in the database and will return back the requested data.
Other Information, Observations, etc.	-

Table 13: Query Builder Capabilities

Capability/ Functionality Title	Description	User roles	Current Maturity/ Readiness (TRL)	Target Maturity/ Readiness (TRL)	Proposed Priority Level	Interface (service, methods, data structures)
Query Builder	It creates an SQL Query taking as input data in JSON format. The current Query Builder works only with tabular data. It should be heavily extended to support health data for the project.	clinician/scientist	TRL 4 - technology validated in lab	TRL 6 - technology demonstrated in relevant environment	Must Have	Not available-We have to investigate the functionalities and the implementation of this component in BDO in order to provide more details

3.5 DATA LAKE - ENG

Table 14: Data Lake Description

Responsible Partner Abbreviated Name (per DoA)	ENG
Technology/Component Name within MES-CoBraD	Data Lake
Technology/Component Other Internal Name	Storage Service (part of Digital Enabler platform)
Corresponding Task in MES-CoBraD	T5.1
Is the technology developed/owned by Responsible Partner or third party?	Custom solution powered by open source software (MinIO)
Current Technology Readiness Level (TRL)	TRL 7 – system prototype demonstration in operational environment
Planned Technology Readiness (TRL) by the end of MES-CoBraD	TRL 8 – system complete and qualified
Technology/Component History	Components developed internally for other research projects and currently also used in other production projects.
Technology/Component in the Present: Description	An AWS S3 compliant object storage that enables to store big amount of data in different file formats.
Technology/Component at the End of Project: Description	No big evolution are planned for this component. It will be the sink that will store the data collected by the connectors
Technology at the End Of Project: Benefits	The data will be stored in a secure way, and will be made available in compliance with the (standard de-factor) AWS S3 specifications for object storages.
Hardware/Networking (Low Level) Interfaces	-
Software Interfaces (protocols, file types, standards)	REST, API, SDK
Other Information, Observations, etc.	-

Table 15: Data Lake Capabilities

Capability/ Functionality Title	Description	User roles	Current Maturity/ Readiness (TRL)	Target Maturity/ Readiness (TRL)	Proposed Priority Level	Interface (service, methods, data structures)
Push Data	Create a new file in a bucket.	User	TRL 7 – system prototype demonstration in operational environment	TRL 8 – system complete and qualified	Must Have	Interfaces are totally compliant with what described here: https://docs.min.io/docs/java-client-quickstart-guide.html . But files are also manageable through web UI
Get Data	Get an already existing file in a bucket	User	TRL 7 – system prototype demonstration in operational environment	TRL 8 – system complete and qualified	Must Have	Interfaces are totally compliant with what described here: https://docs.min.io/docs/java-client-quickstart-guide.html . But files are also manageable through web UI
Delete Data	Remove a file the user owns	User	TRL 7 – system prototype demonstration in operational environment	TRL 8 – system complete and qualified	Must Have	Interfaces are totally compliant with what described here: https://docs.min.io/docs/java-client-quickstart-guide.html . But files are also manageable through web UI
Update Data	Update a file with a newer version	User	TRL 7 – system prototype demonstration in operational environment	TRL 8 – system complete and qualified	Must Have	Interfaces are totally compliant with what described here: https://docs.min.io/docs/java-client-quickstart-guide.html . But files are also manageable through web UI

3.6 DATA HARMONISATION MODULE- ENG

Table 16: Data Harmonisation Module Description

Responsible Partner Abbreviated Name (per DoA)	ENG
Technology/Component Name within MES-CoBraD	Data Harmonisation module
Technology/Component Other Internal Name	Data Mashup Editor (part of Digital Enabler platform)
Corresponding Task in MES-CoBraD	T5.1
Is the technology developed/owned by Responsible Partner or third party?	Solution 100% owned and developed by Engineering
Current Technology Readiness Level (TRL)	TRL 7 – system prototype demonstration in operational environment
Planned Technology Readiness (TRL) by the end of MES-CoBraD	TRL 8 – system complete and qualified
Technology/Component History	Component developed internally for other research projects. The component has been improved over time going through different research and production projects
Technology/Component in the Present: Description	No-Code component for real-time data manipulation and harmonisation
Technology/Component at the End of Project: Description	The component will be enriched with out-of-the-box operators for health standard data models.
Technology at the End Of Project: Benefits	The no-code approach ensures that also non-technical users may understand the logic behind the harmonisation process. Every harmonisation step can be isolated in a "mashup" that is independently maintained.
Hardware/Networking (Low Level) Interfaces	-
Software Interfaces (protocols, file types, standards)	REST
Other Information, Observations, etc.	-

Table 17:Data Harmonisation Module Capabilities

Capability/ Functionality Title	Description	User roles	Current Maturity/ Readiness (TRL)	Target Maturity/ Readiness (TRL)	Proposed Priority Level	Interface (service, methods, data structures)
Manage a Mashup	Create, delete and edit a mashup (a mashup is a process that manipulates data with harmonisation purposes). The business logic of a mashup is defined entirely in a no-code way; it can be done by simply dragging and dropping operators on a working area.	User	TRL 7 – system prototype demonstration in operational environment	TRL 8 – system complete and qualified	Must Have	It can be done on the web UI
Monitor a Mashup	Track the log of each mashup execution	User	TRL 7 – system prototype demonstration in operational environment	TRL 8 – system complete and qualified	Must Have	It can be done on the web UI
Manage data sources	Create, delete and edit a data source to use it in a mashup. (e.g. a rest API to be invoked during the mashup execution flow)	User	TRL 7 – system prototype demonstration in operational environment	TRL 8 – system complete and qualified	Must Have	It can be done on the web UI
Create a mashup trigger	Define which are the possible triggers for a mashup. The possibilities are: schedule interval, HTTP call, MQTT message, Kafka message	User	TRL 7 – system prototype demonstration in operational environment	TRL 8 – system complete and qualified	Must Have	It can be done on the web UI
Create a mashup sink	Define where the mashup result should be published. The possibilities are: HTTP endpoint, MQTT Topic, KAFKA Topic, FIWARE Orion Context Broker	User	TRL 7 – system prototype demonstration in operational environment	TRL 8 – system complete and qualified	Could Have	It can be done on the web UI

3.7 DATA INGESTION MODULE- ENG

Table 18: Data Ingestion Module Description

Responsible Partner Abbreviated Name (per DoA)	ENG
Technology/Component Name within MES-CoBraD	Data Ingestion module
Technology/Component Other Internal Name	Dataflow (part of Digital Enabler platform)
Corresponding Task in MES-CoBraD	T5.1
Is the technology developed/owned by Responsible Partner or third party?	Custom solution powered by open source software (Airflow)
Current Technology Readiness Level (TRL)	TRL 7 – system prototype demonstration in operational environment
Planned Technology Readiness (TRL) by the end of MES-CoBraD	TRL 8 – system complete and qualified
Technology/Component History	Component developed internally for other research projects. The component has been improved over time going through different research and production projects
Technology/Component in the Present: Description	Low-code component for batch data collection
Technology/Component at the End of Project: Description	The component will be enriched with out-of-the-box operators for connection to redcap and other healthcare systems
Technology at the End Of Project: Benefits	The tool allows to have a comprehensive overview over the status of the ingestion processes into the MES-CoBraD platform. Each process can be independently and easily scheduled.
Hardware/Networking (Low Level) Interfaces	-
Software Interfaces (protocols, file types, standards)	REST, SDK
Other Information, Observations, etc.	-

Table 19: Data Ingestion Module Capabilities

Capability/ Functionality Title	Description	User roles	Current Maturity/ Readiness (TRL)	Target Maturity/ Readiness (TRL)	Proposed Priority Level	Interface (service, methods, data structures)
Manage DAG	Create, delete and edit a DAG (a DAG is a Direct Acyclic Graph that represents a data flow with ingestion purposes). The business logic of a mashup is defined entirely in a low-code way, according to a Python-based language.	User	TRL 7 – system prototype demonstration in operational environment	TRL 8 – system complete and qualified	Must Have	Management can be done through a dedicated CLI
Monitor a DAG	Track the log of each mashup execution and the status of each step of the data flow	User	TRL 7 – system prototype demonstration in operational environment	TRL 8 – system complete and qualified	Must Have	It can be done on the web UI

3.8 EXPERT SYSTEM- EVOL

Table 20: Expert System Description

Responsible Partner Abbreviated Name (per DoA)	EVOL
Technology/Component Name within MES-CoBraD	Expert System
Technology/Component Other Internal Name	
Corresponding Task in MES- CoBraD	T6.1
Is the technology developed/owned by Responsible Partner or third party?	Will be developed by EVOL, open source software will be used with open source libraries. Third party apps will be migrated too.
Current Technology Readiness Level (TRL)	TRL 1 – basic principles observed
Planned Technology Readiness (TRL) by the end of MES- CoBraD	TRL 9 – actual system proven in operational environment
Technology/Component History	
Technology/Component in the Present: Description	We are currently researching the right tools (3rd party - open source - libraries) that will be used and create the Expert System Architecture
Technology/Component at the End of Project: Description	The Expert Systems (ES) will provide an alternative methodology in analysing data to identify variables with the highest correlation to the outcome using the most appropriate data analysis and algorithms that Scientists will choose according to the patient circumstances each time. Each scientist will be responsible for creating a flow of processes that must be performed upon admission of the patient and the system based on an artificial intelligence model will suggest to the scientist the next steps. Finally, the system will control the results of clinical and non-clinical processes with the appropriate tools, advancing the situation to next or previous steps.
Technology at the End Of Project: Benefits	The advantage of such a system is the o define and understand their procedures of each case, to provide a standard notation that is easily understood by all stakeholders, to depict the complexities of a process yet is simple enough to understand and save time between each step to be completed, until the final result.
Hardware/Networking (Low Level) Interfaces	
Software Interfaces (protocols, file types, standards)	REST API, MQTT (under consideration), Queuing Mechanism (under consideration), Cron Jobs (under consideration), Docker
Other Information, Observations, etc.	

Table 21: Expert System Capabilities

Capability/ Functionality Title	Description	User roles	Current Maturity/ Readiness (TRL)	Target Maturity/ Readiness (TRL)	Proposed Priority Level	Interface (service, methods, data structures)
BPMN	The primary goal of a Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN) is to support process management for both scientific partners and technical partners. It provides a notation that's intuitive to scientific users but is also able to represent complex process semantics. There are 2 candidates. One is a python library (SpiffWorkflow) and the other one is a independent open source system (Process Maker)	internal process	TRL 1 – basic principles observed	TRL 9 – actual system proven in operational environment	Must Have	
BPMN UI	The user interface and user experience on how the user will create the processes and how he will interact with this system and its requirements	clinician	TRL 1 – basic principles observed	TRL 9 – actual system proven in operational environment	Must Have	
BPMN Process Mining	This system may allow the creation of a workflow based on a table of patients, timestamps and events. An algorithm may find the processes and the connections and create a model of processes that can be used at a later stage. A good candidate is pm4py.	clinician	TRL 1 – basic principles observed	TRL 8 – system complete and qualified	Could Have	

Capability/ Functionality Title	Description	User roles	Current Maturity/ Readiness (TRL)	Target Maturity/ Readiness (TRL)	Proposed Priority Level	Interface (service, methods, data structures)
BPMN Automate Process Management	This system may allow the automation of medical processes. Given a minimum set of patient data, the clinician can initiate the best and most effective workflow process to make a diagnosis or a therapeutic decision.	clinician	TRL 1 – basic principles observed	TRL 3 – experimental proof of concept	Would be Nice	
Queuing System	A system that will handle the internal system commands (e.g. create a process, run this algorithm, etc.). The goal is to split the workload and not overload the system (e.g. if a AI algorithm takes a lot of time to execute, having a queue won't feel so slow or crush). A good candidate is RabbitMQ	internal process	TRL 1 – basic principles observed	TRL 9 – actual system proven in operational environment	Would be Nice	

3.9 ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE- EVOL

Table 22: Artificial Intelligence Description

Responsible Partner Abbreviated Name (per DoA)	EVOL
Technology/Component Name within MES-CoBraD	Artificial Intelligence
Technology/Component Other Internal Name	
Corresponding Task in MES-CoBraD	T6.3
Is the technology developed/owned by Responsible Partner or third party?	Will be developed by EVOL, but many 3rd party - open source - libraries will be used
Current Technology Readiness Level (TRL)	TRL 1 – basic principles observed
Planned Technology Readiness (TRL) by the end of MES-CoBraD	TRL 9 – actual system proven in operational environment
Technology/Component History	
Technology/Component in the Present: Description	We are currently researching the right tools (3rd party - open source - libraries) that will be used and create the AI models
Technology/Component at the End of Project: Description	
Technology at the End Of Project: Benefits	
Hardware/Networking (Low Level) Interfaces	
Software Interfaces (protocols, file types, standards)	REST API, MQTT (under consideration), Queuing Mechanism (under consideration), Docker
Other Information, Observations, etc.	

Table 23: Artificial Intelligence Capabilities

Capability/ Functionality Title	Description	User roles	Current Maturity/ Readiness (TRL)	Target Maturity/ Readiness (TRL)	Proposed Priority Level	Interface (service, methods, data structures)
AI Model System	This should be a modular system that provides diagnosis, prognosis and treatment modules. Each module will contain the AI algorithms that will be used. All algorithms will be implemented as an API, to have a modular approach and allow the addition of some new AI algorithms or libraries in the future		TRL 1 - basic principles observed	TRL 9 - actual system proven in operational environment	Must Have	

4 USER & TECHNICAL REQUIREMENTS

This Chapter represents the main output of the first iteration cycle of T7.1. In other words, it describes the first iteration of the user role definitions and user & technical requirements. As explained in Section 2.4 a variety of instruments for data collection, analysis and collaboration were used to arrive at this first formulation of user roles and requirements.

4.1 UPDATED LIST OF COMPONENTS/TOOLS

In carrying out the requirements analysis and mapping them per components, we identified the need for new system components compared to the ones mentioned in the DoA. Moreover, we identified some small inconsistencies between DoA Part A and Part A in terms of the exact names of the components. That's why we present below in Table 24 an updated list of all Components.

- › The first two columns present the names of components as mentioned in DoA Part B and Part A.
- › The third column presents a “new component name” which is the final name adopted, relevant when there were inconsistencies between the two parts of the DoA. These are the names which shall be used from here on for the MES-CoBraD System Components/Tools. Also, the new components (which were not mentioned previously in the DoA) appear with “NA” (not available) in the first two columns and they only have a name in the third column.
- › Furthermore, the 4th column contains a 2 or 3 letter code associated to each component. These were also useful to further encode the functional requirements.
- › Finally, the components are mapped to the Tasks where they will be implemented and the partners responsible for those tasks.

Table 24: List of Components

Component name per DoA Part B	Component name per DoA Part A	New component name	Code	Task #	Responsible partner
API Gateway	FIWARE GE	API Gateway	APG	T5.1	ENG
Auditing	NA	Auditing	AUD	T7.3	SIMAVI
Explorative Analytics	Data Analytics	Data Analytics	DAN	T6.2	NTUA
Data Collection	Data Collection	Data collection	DCO	T5.1	ENG
Data Harmonisation	Data Harmonisation	Data Harmonisation	DHA	T5.1	ENG
Data lake/ Data storage	Data lake	Data lake	DLK	T5.1	ENG
Expert System	Expert System	Expert System	ES	T6.1	EVOL
NA	NA	Local back end	LBE	T5.2	ENG
Machine Learning	Artificial Intelligence	Machine Learning	ML	T6.3	EVOL
NA	NA	Metadata Management	MDM	T5.1	ENG
NA	NA	MRI Quality control module	MRQ	T7.3	SIMAVI
Policy Annotation	Policy Annotation	Policy Annotation	POA	T5.2	ENG
Privacy	Anonymisation	Privacy Manager	PRM	T5.2	ENG
NA	NA	Query Builder	QRB	T6.2	NTUA
NA	NA	Questionnaire Builder	QSB	T7.3	SIMAVI
Resource sharing	Resource sharing	Resource sharing	RSH	T5.3	ENG
NA	NA	User Management and Access Control	UMA	T7.3	ENG
Visualisation Dashboards	Visualisation Dashboards	Visualisation Dashboards	VDS	T6.2	NTUA
NA	NA	Integrated Solution	INS	T7.3	SIMAVI

4.2 USER ROLES

Table 25 presents the list of user roles and their definitions as they were identified in the requirements analysis process. Functional requirements presented in the next Section were mapped to these user roles. This mapping is necessary for user management and access control.

Table 25: User Roles

Name	Description
System administrator	A person who is responsible for the upkeep, configuration, and reliable operation of computer systems, especially multi-user computers, such as servers.
Scientist coordinator	A person who conducts scientific research in an area of interest and aims to coordinate the task and must ensure that everything goes well.
Scientist	A person who conducts scientific research to advance knowledge in an area of interest.
Clinician	A doctor having direct contact with patients rather than being involved with theoretical or laboratory studies.
Caregiver	A person who gives care to people who need help taking care of themselves. They may give care at home or in a hospital or other health care setting.
Patient	A person who suffers from a condition and is being treated by a doctor.

4.3 FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

As mentioned in Section 2.2 above, *Functional Requirements* “describe the capabilities that a solution must have in terms of the behaviour and information that the solution will manage” (International Institute of Business Analysis, 2015, p. 16).

Following the process of elicitation and analysis of requirements a total number of 102 functional requirements resulted, which were distributed rather unevenly between components (as shown in Table 26 below). This information is given for a general overview; however, it should be noted that requirements are not comparable between them. A high number of requirements may suggest that requirements in that case are formulated in a more granular fashion as the types of functionalities allowed further split. Number of requirements by itself is not necessarily indicative of the “amount of work” needed for the analysis or development of each component.

Table 26: Number of Functional Requirements by System Components

Component	No. of Requirements
API Gateway	1
Auditing	4
Data Analytics	11
Data collection	5
Data harmonisation	9
Data lake	6
Expert System	17
Integrated Solution	2
Local back end: Edge computing scenarios	1
Machine Learning	8
Metadata Management	5
MRI Quality control module	1
Policy Annotation	2
Privacy Manager	2
Query Builder	1
Questionnaire Builder	4
Resource sharing	2
User Management and Access Control	13
Visualisation Dashboards	8
Grand Total	102

In presenting the requirements we considered several modes of presentation/formalisation. We considered and initially used for the first few requirements *user stories* as a way of describing requirements. However, since we needed to include both user facing and non-user facing requirements in the overall list, we decided against the use of user stories which can only describe user facing requirements. We opted for a list presentation of requirements where their description employs a classical formulation “the system shall” followed by the verb characterising the action. (All requirements initially formulated as user stories were converted).

Most work on requirements was carried out in an Excel document which was shared online in our collaborative SharePoint platform (this document can be made available to the project officer and monitors upon request). The Excel table of requirements contained the following columns (i.e the following information items that were collected about requirements):

- A. *Code* – a 2 or 3 letter code associated to each component (as shown in Table 24 above)
- B. *No* – a number associated to each requirement. This number is incremented for each requirement for the same component. Therefore, the unique identification of a requirement is based on the alphanumeric Code plus the numeric No.
- C. *Title* – a title of the requirement.
- D. *Description* – the description of the requirement
- E. *Relevant DoA Content* – for requirements which were derived straight from the DoA, the relevant DoA content (quotes) were pasted in this column.
- F. *Comments, details observations*: relevant comments which appeared in the discussion of requirements.
- G. *Depends on*: this column is reserved for dependencies between requirements, yet it is not

completed at this point. Further work in detailing requirements under component implementation tasks shall add information here.

H. *User Facing*: indicates if the requirement is user facing or not (Yes/No), i.e. whether a requirement is regarding something visible to the user (e.g. elements of interface, inputs, outputs) or something that is invisible to the user (back end aspects such as communication between components, operations etc.).

I. *User Role(s)*: indicates the user roles who will have access and use the functionality corresponding to the requirement.

J. *Component* – the complete name of the component to which the requirement corresponds.

K. *Task*: indicates the task number under which the component is developed.

L. *Task name*: The full name of the task under which the component is developed.

M. *Task Leader*: – the task leader responsible for the task where the component is being implemented.

N. *Technical Partners Priority*: indicates the priority level of the requirement as proposed by the technological partner in charge of the component.

O. *NIA Priority*: indicates the priority level as proposed by scientific/end user partner NIA

P. *UU Priority*: indicates the priority level as proposed by scientific/end user partner UU.

Q. *IR-HSCSP Priority*: indicates the priority level as proposed by scientific/end user partner IR-HSCSP

R. *KCL Priority*: indicates the priority level as proposed by scientific/end user partner KCL

S. *UEDIN Priority*: indicates the priority level as proposed by scientific/end user partner UEDIN

T. *CHS-RMC Priority*: indicates the priority level as proposed by scientific/end user partner CHS-RMC.

From the above list, only the items written in black were included in the tables of functional requirements in the following sections of this chapter. This is for several reasons:

1. Overall, we had less “real estate” in a Word Document than in an Excel document, so we had to be selective in terms of what information to present in these tables.
2. Some columns alternate between containing excessive amount of text which is not useful for a report format and no text at all (this is the case of columns E and F).
3. Column G is a placeholder which contains no information at this point.
4. Columns I, L and M have redundant information with K (for this report we chose to present only the task code and not its full name and the leader – information which is available in the DoA).

The issue of prioritisation requires additional methodological explanation. For prioritising requirements, we used the MoSCoW method and scale of prioritisation. MoSCoW is an iterative method of prioritising requirements. It “provides a way to reach a common understanding of relative importance of delivering” functionalities corresponding to requirements (International Institute of Business Analysis, 2015, p. 375). It is often associated with agile techniques but can be used in other contexts as well. MoSCoW provides the following scale:

1. *Must have*: is a feature that must be implemented and is part of the minimum number of features of a system at launch.
2. *Should have*: these requirements are important but not necessary for the current delivery.
3. *Could have*: such requirements are desirable and could add value, they will be included if time and resources permit.
4. *Would be nice* (sometimes also termed *Won't have*): these are requirements are least important at the time and will not be included in this implementation.

We employed this scale of prioritisation, and as a first iteration we asked all partners: on the one hand technological partners (only for the requirements for the components they are in charge of implementing) and scientific/end user partners (for requirements for all components except the non-user facing ones) to propose a priority level. We present this raw data as a first iteration representing the “proposed” priority levels of the different stakeholders. In many cases there is an overall agreement between partners regarding the priority levels, in others there are differences. At this stage we did not yet attempt to arrive at uniform agreed priorities between partners where disagreements may exist. We believe it is appropriate to discuss, arbitrate and negotiate these differences as work progresses toward more clearly defining components (under WPs 5, 6 and 7) and planning the sprints for their implementation.

As you will observe, for some requirements there are some missing data regarding prioritisation by Scientific/End User Partners. They are missing for 2 reasons:

1. For obvious reasons Scientific/End User Partners were not asked to prioritise non-user facing requirements.
2. To ask for Scientific Partners’ prioritisation of requirements, a version of the list of requirements was saved (i.e. frozen at a moment in time) and columns for prioritisation by scientific partners. After that moment, the original list of requirements further evolved, and more requirements were added. For those newly added requirements data about prioritisation by Scientific Requirements does not exist yet. However, we are in the process of further asking Scientific Partners for a second pass through the more complete list of requirements and add prioritisation data where missing.

4.3.1 API GATEWAY COMPONENT REQUIREMENTS

Table 27: API Gateway Component Requirements

Code	No	Title	Description	User facing? (Yes/No)	User role(s)	Task	Technical Partners Priority	NIA Priority	UU Priority	IR-HSCSP Priority	KCL Priority	UEDIN Priority	CHS-RMC Priority
APG	1	API Gateway	The system shall make available an API Gateway according to OpenAPI specifications, exposing project information and allowing data collection in a standard and simple way to facilitate access.	No	None	T5.1	Must have						

4.3.2 AUDITING COMPONENT REQUIREMENTS

Table 28: Auditing Component Requirements

Code	No	Title	Description	User facing? (Yes/No)	User role(s)	Task	Technical Partners Priority	NIA Priority	UU Priority	IR-HSCSP Priority	KCL Priority	UEDIN Priority	CHS-RMC Priority
AUD	1	Policy enforcement	The system shall ensure that access to data shall be granted based on data licensing.	No	None	T7.3	Must have						
AUD	2	Data auditing of edge module personal data access	The system shall ensure auditing of personal data accessed by the edge module at row level by recording audit trails for chronological events or procedures to provide support documentation and history for security and operational actions, providing proof of data origin and integrity.	No	None	T7.3	Must have						
AUD	3	Data auditing of platform related events	The system shall audit other types of events (data driven operations).	No	None	T7.3	Should have						
AUD	4	View data auditing log	The system shall allow to view data auditing log.	Yes	System Admin	T7.3	Must have	Could have		Must have	Must have	Should have	

4.3.3 DATA ANALYTICS COMPONENT REQUIREMENTS

Table 29: Data Analytics Component Requirements

Code	No	Title	Description	User facing? (Yes/No)	User role(s)	Task	Technical Partners Priority	NIA Priority	UU Priority	IR-HSCSP Priority	KCL Priority	UEDIN Priority	CHS-RMC Priority
DAN	1	Time-Series Analysis	The System shall ensure Time-Series Analysis for measuring longitudinal data at regular time intervals, in order to support the study of CoBraD. It will include various techniques such as such as: identification of potential changes in patients' data over time, pattern recognition and identification of hidden associations among variables, extraction of meaningful statistics, early prediction of future patient data, accurate evaluation of the impact of lifestyle, environmental and health /pharmaceutical variables to CoBraD outcomes.	No	None	T6.2	Must have						
DAN	2	Posterior probabilities of next steps	The system shall calculate posterior probabilities of proposed next steps.	No	None	T6.2	Should have						
DAN	3	Option for randomisation of participants into an intervention	The system shall randomise participants into an intervention.	Yes	Scientist/ Clinician	T6.2	Would be nice						
DAN	4	Support ES - Guided steps	The system shall permit the user to be informed by the ES on the next recommended diagnostic step, so as depending on the data available to the ES at any given time, it can start forming hypotheses based on the	Yes	Clinician-Scientist, Patient/ Caregiver	T6.2	Should have						

			"chief complaint" and "deep-phenotype" of a patient and instruct on accessing missing variables.										
DAN	5	Recommend analysis types	The system shall include statistical packages available as modules from which to select functions that can be part of an analysis process.	Yes	Scientist/ Clinician	T6.2	Must have	Must have	Must have	Could have	Must have	Must have	Must have
DAN	6	Selection of cases based on inclusion and exclusion criteria	The system shall allow to be select cases based on inclusion and exclusion criteria (upon performing an analysis, select whom you will study based on x, y, z criteria).	Yes	Scientist/ Clinician	T6.2	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have
DAN	7	Data manipulation plug-ins	The system shall allow scientists to install plug-ins that would provide black box functionalities offered by the community.	Yes	Scientist/ Clinician	T6.2	Would be nice	Should have	Would be nice	Must have	Should have	Should have	Would be nice
DAN	8	Integrate Opensource modules for EEG/PSG, but also MRI data	The system shall integrate Opensource modules for EEG/PSG, but also MRI data.	Yes	Scientist/ Clinician	T6.2	Should have	Should have		Must have	Must have	Could have	Must have
DAN	9	Traits for steps in a process - selection of variables by class	The system shall permit while examining if a hypothesis can be rejected, then select one or more sets of variables according to the "class" (Annex I traits) that they have.	Yes	Scientist/ Clinician	T6.2	Would be nice	Must have	Must have	Could have	Should have	Could have	Should have
DAN	10	Hypothesis development and testing - High level associations	The system shall be able to identify a protocol developed by the user, and either through supervised or unsupervised processes, develop hypotheses (e.g., is independent Variable Set A related to dependent Variable Set B), or test these hypotheses.	Yes	Scientist/ Clinician	T6.2	Must have	Could have	Would be nice	Would be nice	Should have	Could have	Should have
DAN	11	Generation of a report as output	it is important to generate a type of report when performing the analysis where one could find information on	Yes	Scientist/ Clinician	T6.2	Must have						

			which method was used, version of the programming language and version of the pipeline/package, because these details (specially the versions) are always required by the reviewers/editors for publication in the paper-methods section.										
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4.3.4 DATA COLLECTION COMPONENT REQUIREMENTS

Table 30: Data Collection Component Requirements

Code	No	Title	Description	User facing? (Yes/No)	User role(s)	Task	Technical Partners Priority	NIA Priority	UU Priority	IR-HSCSP Priority	KCL Priority	UEDIN Priority	CHS-RMC Priority
DCO	1	Data collection	The system shall collect and integrate data from various legacy and external systems using a common and standard based data framework.	No	None	T5.1	Must have						
DCO	2	Data Collection Configuration	The system shall allow users to configure the data being collected.	Yes	System admin, Science coordinator, patients	T5.1	Should have	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have	Should have
DCO	3	Manage DAG	The system allows the user to create, delete and edit a DAG (a DAG is a Direct Acyclic Graph that represents a data flow with ingestion purposes). The business logic of a mashup is defined entirely in a low-code way, according to a python-based language.	Yes	System admin	T5.1	Must have	Should have	Would be nice	Could have	Must have	Should have	Should have
DCO	4	Monitor a DAG	The system allows the user to track the log of each mashup execution and the status of each step of the data flow	Yes	System admin	T5.1	Must have	Should have	Must have		Must have	Should have	Should have
DCO	5	Developer tool - New RWD type	The system shall allow to introduce new RWD types (e.g. cardiac Holter). This type of data can also be used in a flexible platform.	Yes	Clinician-Scientist, Platform developer	T5.1	Would be nice						

4.3.5 DATA HARMONISATION COMPONENT REQUIREMENT

Table 31: Data Harmonisation Component Requirements

Code	No	Title	Description	User facing? (Yes/ No)	User role(s)	Task	Technical Partners Priority	NIA Priority	UU Priority	IR-HSCSP Priority	KCL Priority	UEDIN Priority	CHS-RMC Priority
DHA	1	Data Harmonisation	The system shall harmonise and transform the collected data into a standard format, using an internal data model that will be defined during the project.	No	None	T5.1	Must have						
DHA	2	Data Harmonisation Configuration	The system shall provide users with an interface to configure and view process of harmonisation.	Yes	System admin; Science coordinator	T5.1	Should have	Must have	Must have	Could have	Must have	Should have	Must have
DHA	3	Manage a Mashup	The system shall allow the user to create, delete and edit a mashup (a mashup is a process that manipulates data with harmonisation purposes). The business logic of a mashup is defined entirely in a no-code way; it can be done by simply dragging and dropping operators on a working area.	Yes	System admin; Science coordinator; Scientist	T5.1	Must have	Should have	Should have	Could have	Must have	Should have	
DHA	4	Monitor a Mashup	The system shall allow the user to track the log of each mashup execution.	Yes	System admin; Science coordinator; Scientist	T5.1	Would be nice	Should have	Should have	Must have	Should have	Should have	
DHA	5	Manage datasources	The system shall allow the user to create, delete and edit a data source to use it in a mashup. (e.g. a rest api to be invoked during the mashup execution flow).	Yes	System admin; Science coordinator; Scientist	T5.1	Must have	Should have	Should have	Could have	Must have	Should have	
DHA	6	Create a mashup	The system shall allow the user to define which are the possible	Yes	System admin; Science	T5.1	Must have	Could have	Should have		Should have		

		trigger	triggers for a mashup. The possibilities are: schedule interval, http call, mqtt message, kafka message.		coordinator; Scientist									
DHA	7	Create a mashup sink	The system shall allow the user to define where the mashup result should be published. The possibilities are: HTTP endpoint, MQTT Topic, KAFKA Topic, FIWARE Orion Context Broker.	Yes	System admin; Science coordinator; Scientist	T5.1	Would be nice		Should have		Should have			
DHA	8	Common contextual data framework	The system shall design and develop in a common contextual framework the collected, harmonised and RWD data, integrating and connecting them efficiently to ensure the interoperability of the data.	No	None	T5.1	Must have							
DHA	9	Missing data treatment	The system shall provide functions to impute missing data.	Yes	Scientist/Clinician	T5.1	Should have	Should have	Must have	Must have	Must have	Could have	Must have	

4.3.6 DATA LAKE COMPONENT REQUIREMENTS

Table 32: Data Lake Component Requirements

Code	No	Title	Description	User facing? (Yes/ No)	User role(s)	Task	Technical Partners Priority	NIA Priority	UU Priority	IR-HSCSP Priority	KCL Priority	UEDIN Priority	CHS-RMC Priority
DLK	1	Data storage	The system shall store data collected from heterogenous outside data sources (RWD) and from outputs of the system in Data Lake solution.	No	None	T5.1	Must have						
DLK	2	Management of Stored Data	The system shall allow users to manage data stored from heterogeneous external data sources (RWD).	Yes	System Administrator	T5.1	Must have	Must have	Must have	Should have	Must have	Must have	
DLK	3	Push Data	The system shall create a new file in a bucket.	Yes	system admin + components	T5.1	Must have						
DLK	4	Get Data	The system shall get an already existing file in a bucket.	Yes	system admin + components	T5.1	Must have						
DLK	5	Delete Data	The system shall remove a file the user owns.	Yes	system admin + components	T5.1	Must have						
DLK	6	Update Data	The system shall update a file with a newer version.	Yes	system admin + components	T5.1	Must have						

4.3.7 EXPERT SYSTEM COMPONENT REQUIREMENTS

Table 33: Expert System Component Requirements

Code	No	Title	Description	User facing? (Yes/No)	User role(s)	Task	Technical Partners Priority	NIA Priority	UU Priority	IR-HSCSP Priority	KCL Priority	UEDIN Priority	CHS-RMC Priority
ES	1	Expert System	The system shall provide an Expert System to guide clinical decisions by providing feedback from both patients and clinicians.	Yes	Clinician	T6.1	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have		Must have	Must have
ES	2	Flexible steps sequence within processes	The system shall allow for flexibility of relations of priority and posteriority between steps in processes.	Yes	Scientist/ Clinician	T6.1	Should have	Should have		Should have	Should have		Should have
ES	3	Visualisation per Step of DSS/ES output	The system shall provide to the user the ability to have a visual comprehension of the posterior probabilities of the proposed next step(s) - cutoff for highest probability next steps, for each decision(s) the ES makes.	Yes	Scientist/ Clinician	T6.1	Must have	Could have	Should have	Could have		Would be nice	Should have
ES	4	User control over next step(s) of DSS/ES	The system shall allow the user to choose the next step (from the list or outside it), depending on options provided in Visualisation per Step of DSS/ES output.	Yes	Scientist/ Clinician	T6.1	Must have	Should have	Should have	Could have	Should have	Would be nice	Must have
ES	5	Coordination aide module -scheduling	The system shall allow the coordinator/user to be informed of upcoming steps (e.g., scheduling a specific participant, or calling someone), based on the pilot protocol process of a study.	Yes	Scientist/ Clinician	T6.1	Could have	Should have	Should have			Would be nice	Must have
ES	6	Coordination aide module - progress/monitoring	The system shall provide feedback on the progress of recruited participants and participants	Yes	Scientist/ Clinician	T6.1	Could have	Should have	Would be nice	Should have	Should have	Should have	Would be nice

			performing various tests.										
ES	7	Option for randomisation of participants into an intervention	The system shall randomise participants into an intervention.	Yes	Scientist/ Clinician	T6.1	Could have	Would be nice	Would be nice	Could have	Would be nice	Would be nice	Should have
ES	8	Developer tool - Protocols	The system shall allow to create a flow of actions that reflect a protocol (e.g., PUC1) including timelines, processes. Harmonized protocols can be achieved within and across sites, and ES can identify types of variables present (or missing), to pursue recommendations and analyses.	Yes	Scientist/ Clinician	T6.1	Must have	Should have	Would be nice	Should have	Should have	Could have	Should have
ES	9	Visualise flow of actions	The system shall allow to visualise flow of actions that reflect the protocol.	Yes	Scientist/ Clinician	T6.1	Must have	Should have	Would be nice	Could have	Would be nice	Should have	Should have
ES	10	Observed and latent variables	The ES shall be able to consider / use both simple / observed and complex / latent decision variables	Yes	Scientist/ Clinician	T6.1	Must have	Should have	Must have			Could have	Must have
ES	11	Selection and execution analytical processes	The system shall allow the user to create a workflow in which every step will have a function for performing a specific analysis task from modules/packages analysis.	No	None	T6.1	Must have						
ES	12	UI for selecting analytical processes	The system shall allow the user to create a workflow in which every step will have a function for performing a specific analysis task from modules/packages analysis.	Yes	Scientist/ Clinician	T6.1	Must have	Must have		Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have
ES	13	ES - Guided steps	The system shall permit the user to be informed by the ES on the next recommended diagnostic step, so as depending on the data available to the ES at any given time, it can start forming hypotheses based on the "chief complaint" and "deep-phenotype" of a patient and instruct	Yes	Clinician- Scientist, Patient/ Caregiver	T6.1	Should have	Should have	Could have	Must have	Must have	Should have	Must have

			on accessing missing variables.										
ES	14	Automated report/message generator	The system shall generate a report either for feedback to the patient or for use by a clinician, based on the data entered in a specific function.	Yes	Scientist/ Clinician/ Patient	T6.1	Could have	Would be nice		Must have	Could have	Would be nice	Should have
ES	15	Communicate with patients at key times	The system shall ensure communication with patients at key times.	Yes	Scientist/ Clinician/ Patient	T6.1	Would be nice	Would be nice		Would be nice		Would be nice	Would be nice
ES	16	Diagnostic Guidelines Reference Links	The system shall permit to introduce diagnostic guideline libraries in the Platform for being referenced against by the ES in making possible diagnoses.	Yes	Scientist/ Clinician	T6.1	Should have	Must have		Should have	Must have	Must have	
ES	17	Therapeutic Guidelines	The system shall allow to introduce specific recommended therapies according to specific diagnoses / phenotypes, so when using the platform, the user will be informed if a specific therapy can be considered.	Yes	Scientist/ Clinician	T6.1	Must have	Would be nice	Must have	Could have	Should have	Should have	Should have

4.3.8 LOCAL BACK END

Table 34: Local Back End

Code	No	Title	Description	User facing? (Yes/No)	User role(s)	Task	Technical Partners Priority	NIA Priority	UU Priority	IR-HSCSP Priority	KCL Priority	UEDIN Priority	CHS-RMC Priority
LBE	1	Local RWD Anonymisation	The system shall permit the user to be able to use a local script/app/executable in scope of automatically anonymise/deface/etc. local RWD before they are uploaded in the system.	Yes	Scientist/ Clinician	T5.2	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have	Should have	Must have

4.3.9 MACHINE LEARNING COMPONENT REQUIREMENTS

Table 35: Machine Learning Component Requirements

Code	No	Title	Description	User facing? (Yes/No)	User role(s)	Task	Technical Partners Priority	NIA Priority	UU Priority	IR-HSCSP Priority	KCL Priority	UEDIN Priority	CHS-RMC Priority
ML	1	Machine Learning based analysis of data lake	The system have to use Machine Learning technique for delivering added value and analysis to data from data lake	No	None	T6.3	Must have						
ML	2	Machine Learning as a service via an open API	The system have to offer Machine learning as a Service capabilities provided by a dedicated and Open API-based platform.	No	None	T6.1	Must have						
ML	3	AI based natural language processing	The system shall include an open source algorithm/platform (previously developed on the FITMAN project) which shall analyse natural language (via natural language processing) coming from social media content using techniques/algorithms like machine learning, sentiment analysis, correlation mining.	No	None	T6.3	Could have						
ML	4	AI based natural language processing reports	The system shall produce customisable/configurable reports, dashboards and visualisations based on NLP analysis	Yes	Scientist	T6.3	Could have	Would be nice	Would be nice	Would be nice	Could Have		Would be nice

ML	5	AI based process optimisation	The system shall optimise process steps sequences in Expert System based on prior information about steps effectiveness.	Yes	Scientist/Clinician	T6.3	Should have	Must have	Must have	Should Have	Could Have	Must have	Must have
ML	6	AI based process optimisation	The system shall optimise process steps sequences in Expert System based on prior information about steps effectiveness.	Yes	Scientist/Clinician	T6.1	Should have						
ML	7	Posterior probabilities of next steps	The system shall calculate posterior probabilities of proposed next steps.	No	None	T6.1	Should have						
ML	8	Support ES - Guided steps	The system shall permit the user to be informed by the ES on the next recommended diagnostic step, so as depending on the data available to the ES at any given time, it can start forming hypotheses based on the "chief complaint" and "deep-phenotype" of a patient, and instruct on accessing missing variables.	Yes	Clinician-Scientist, Patient/ Caregiver	T6.3	Should have						

4.3.10 METADATA MANAGEMENT COMPONENT REQUIREMENTS

Table 36: Metadata Management Component Requirements

Code	No	Title	Description	User facing? (Yes/ No)	User role(s)	Task	Technical Partners Priority	NIA Priority	UU Priority	IR-HSCSP Priority	KCL Priority	UEDIN Priority	CHS-RMC Priority
MDM	1	Create new variables	The system shall permit to create new variables within the platform, for being used in clinical or research protocols.	Yes	Scientist/ Clinician	T5.1	Must have						
MDM	2	Create new variables	The system shall permit to create new variables within the platform, for being used in clinical or research protocols.	Yes	Scientist/ Clinician	T5.1	Must have	Must have	Would be nice	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have
MDM	3	Developer tool - New RWD type	The system shall allow to introduce new RWD types (e.g, cardiac Holter). This type of data can also be used in a flexible platform.	Yes	Clinician-Scientist, Platform developer	T5.1	Would be nice	Would be nice	Would be nice	Must have	Must have	Could have	
MDM	4	Develop latent variables	The System shall ensure the developing of latent variables from existing LVx level variables based on certain function that the user defines.	Yes	Scientist/ Clinician	T5.1	Should have						
MDM	5	Feature to define for a specific user metadata (e.g., QC flag) for a variable or set of variables	The system shall permit to the user to introduce a module or function for identifying a feature of a value in a variable or set of variables and to keep a metadatum on that value(s) (usually for quality control).	Yes	Scientist/ Clinician	T5.1	Would be nice	Must have	Must have	Should have	Could have	Could have	Should have

4.3.11 MRI QUALITY CONTROL MODULE

Table 37: MRI Quality Control Module

Code	No	Title	Description	User facing? (Yes/ No)	User role(s)	Task	Technical Partners Priority	NIA Priority	UU Priority	IR-HSCSP Priority	KCL Priority	UEDIN Priority	CHS-RMC Priority
MRQ	1	QC of MRI data	The System shall compute metrics of Quality for MRI to assess its viability to be used for further analytical modules, using MRIQC tool.	No	None	T7.3		Should have	Would be nice	Should have	Must have	Could have	Should have

4.3.12 POLICY ANNOTATION COMPONENT REQUIREMENTS

Table 38: Policy Annotation Component Requirements

Code	No	Title	Description	User facing? (Yes/ No)	User role(s)	Task	Technical Partners Priority	NIA Priority	UU Priority	IR- HSCSP Priority	KCL Priority	UEDIN Priority	CHS- RMC Priority
POA	1	Policy enforcement	The system shall ensure that access to data shall be granted based on data licensing.	No	None	T5.2	Must have						
POA	2	Policy annotation	The system shall allow users to input data about data licensing and policies.	Yes	Scientist/Clinician	T5.2	Could have	Should have	Must have	Could have	Should have	Must have	Must have

4.3.13 PRIVACY MANAGER COMPONENT REQUIREMENTS

Table 39: Privacy Manager Component Requirements

Code	No	Title	Description	User facing? (Yes/ No)	User role(s)	Task	Technical Partners Priority	NIA Priority	UU Priority	IR-HSCSP Priority	KCL Priority	UEDIN Priority	CHS-RMC Priority
PRM	1	Data Anonymisation and/or Pseudonymisation	The system shall anonymise or pseudonymise (as appropriate and technically feasible) private and/or confidential data.	No	None	T5.2	Must have						
PRM	2	Data Encryption at storage	The system shall encrypt (where appropriate) private and confidential data in the data lake	No	None	T5.2	Must have						

4.3.14 QUERY BUILDER COMPONENT REQUIREMENTS

Table 40: Query Builder Component Requirements

Code	No	Title	Description	User facing? (Yes/ No)	User role(s)	Task	Technical Partners Priority	NIA Priority	UU Priority	IR-HSCSP Priority	KCL Priority	UEDIN Priority	CHS-RMC Priority
QRB	1	Build query	The system shall allow to create an SQL Query taking as input data in JSON format. The current Query Builder works only with tabular data. It should be heavily extended to support health data for the project.	Yes	Scientist/ Clinician	T6.2	Must have				Could have	Would be nice	

4.3.15 QUESTIONNAIRE BUILDER COMPONENT REQUIREMENTS

Table 41: Questionnaire Builder Component Requirements

Code	No	Title	Description	User facing? (Yes/No)	User role(s)	Task	Technical Partners Priority	NIA Priority	UU Priority	IR-HSCSP Priority	KCL Priority	UEDIN Priority	CHS-RMC Priority
QSB	1	Complex questionnaires and question trees	The system shall allow to create complex questionnaires and question trees for Patient/Caregiver and add them to the platform (The questionnaires help to evaluate the patient - to establish the diagnosis and the applied protocol. The questionnaires are made taking into account the sections of Annex 1 - Data Abstraction Categories from D3.2 - Project Manual – CoBraD RWD, Updated MES-CoBraD Protocols and Quality and Quantity (Q&Q) Evaluation).	Yes	Scientist/ Clinician	T7.3	Must have	Must have	Would be nice	Must have	Could have	Must have	Must have
QSB	2	Completing the questionnaires and registering on the platform	The system shall allow the Patient/Caregiver to complete the questionnaires and send/register them on the platform.	Yes	Patient/ Caregiver	T7.3	Must have	Must have	Would be nice	Must have	Would be nice	Must have	Must have
QSB	3	Interpretation and evaluation of the questionnaires	The system shall permit the clinician to interpret and evaluate the data provided by the patient/caregiver in the questionnaire in order to diagnose and establish the protocol based on the information in the questionnaire.	Yes	Scientist/ Clinician	T7.3	Should have	Could have	Must have	Must have	Should have	Could have	Must have
QSB	4	Developer tool - User feedback	The system shall provide feedback to users (patients/caregivers primarily) on the meaning of the data they have entered in order to be able to correct their answers if not reflective of what they intended to say.	Yes	Patient/ Caregiver	T7.3	Should have	Could have	Could have	Must have	Would be nice	Would be nice	

4.3.16 RESOURCE SHARING COMPONENT REQUIREMENTS

Table 42: Resource Sharing Component Requirements

Code	No	Title	Description	User facing? (Yes/No)	User role(s)	Task	Technical Partners Priority	NIA Priority	UU Priority	IR-HSCSP Priority	KCL Priority	UEDIN Priority	CHS-RMC Priority
RSH	1	Sharing artificial intelligence algorithms and datasets and exploiting the produced algorithms	The system shall allow scientists to share artificial intelligence algorithms and datasets, and developers to exploit (and run on platform) the produced algorithms in an easy way.	Yes	Scientist	T6.3	Must have	Must have	Could have	Could have		Should have	Should have
RSH	2	Sharing the derived analyses	The system shall ensure the possibility to share the derived analyses from collected, acquired, linked and integrated data among stakeholders.	Yes	Scientist	T6.3	Must have	Must have	Must have	Would have	Should have	Must have	Must have

4.3.17 USER MANAGEMENT AND ACCESS CONTROL COMPONENT REQUIREMENTS

Table 43: User Management and Access Control Component Requirements

Code	No	Title	Description	User facing? (Yes/No)	User role(s)	Task	Technical Partners Priority	NIA Priority	UU Priority	IR-HSCSP Priority	KCL Priority	UEDIN Priority	CHS-RMC Priority
UMA	1	Sign in	The system shall allow the creation/self-creation of users, shall allow users to securely login into the system based on the credentials, shall assign users to various user roles.	Yes	User	T7.3	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have
UMA	2	Log out	The system shall allow the user to exit from the system.	Yes	User	T7.3	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have
UMA	3	Edit profile	Each user in the system should be able to change some profile data (e.g. username, password)	Yes	User	T7.3	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have
UMA	4	Create account	The system admin will be able to manually create a new user on the platform.	Yes	System admin	T7.3	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have
UMA	5	Delete account	The system admin will be able to manually delete a user from the platform	Yes	System admin	T7.3	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have
UMA	6	Delete own account	Each user in the system will be able to remove his own account exercising his right to be forgotten	Yes	User	T7.3	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have
UMA	7	Suspend account	A system admin should be able to suspend an account. Preventing the associated user to access the platform	Yes	System admin	T7.3	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have
UMA	8	Create a group	A system admin should be able to create a group that can be used to group users of the platform according to arbitrary policies	Yes	System admin	T7.3	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have

UMA	9	Delete a group	A system admin can delete a group.	Yes	System admin	T7.3	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have
UMA	10	Add users to groups	A system admin can associate a user to one or more groups. Each group can contain multiple users	Yes	System admin	T7.3	Must have						
UMA	11	Assign user roles to users	Each user will be associated with a role in the platform.	Yes	System admin	T7.3	Must have	Must have	Could have	Should have	Must have	Must have	Must have
UMA	12	Access control	The system will grant access to its various resources based on users' roles.	No	None	T7.3	Must have						
UMA	13	Guest registers into the platform as doctor	The system shall allow users to be able to register autonomously on the MES-CoBraD platform by using personal (or business) email.	Yes	Scientist/ Clinician/ Patient/ Caregiver	T7.3	Must have						

4.3.18 VISUALISATION DASHBOARDS COMPONENT REQUIREMENTS

Table 44: Visualisation Dashboards Component Requirements

Code	No	Title	Description	User facing? (Yes/ No)	User role(s)	Task	Technical Partners Priority	NIA Priority	UU Priority	IR-HSCSP Priority	KCL Priority	UEDIN Priority	CHS-RMC Priority
VDS	1	Visualisation Dashboards	The system shall store data collected from heterogenous outside data sources (RWD) and from outputs of the system in Data Lake solution.	Yes	Scientist/ Clinician/ Patient/ Caregiver	T6.2	Should have	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have	Must have
VDS	2	Data visualisation - time series	The system shall display time series (e.g., actigraphy data, wearable data, eeg) of n number of variables through bars or lines (x axis for time, y for metric)	Yes	Scientist/ Clinician	T6.2	Must have	Should have	Must have	Should have	Must have	Would be nice	Should have
VDS	3	Data visualisation - interface - select data	The system shall allow to highlight a part of a graph that it's to be labelled. (Depending on the label data the user may decide what to do with it. This could be for example a period in a time series, a point in a scatterplot.)	Yes	Scientist/ Clinician	T6.2	Should have	Could have	Must have	Should have	Must have	Would be nice	Should have
VDS	4	Data visualisation - interface - label data	The system shall allow user after selecting a part of a time series to be able to label the data, i.e. associate a text to the selection.	Yes	Scientist/ Clinician	T6.2	Should have	Could have	Could have	Would be nice	Must have	Could have	Should have
VDS	5	Data visualisation - visualise patient data	The system shall allow the scientist to query all the data available from the patient in order to view them in dashboard.	Yes	Scientist/ Clinician	T6.2	Should have	Should have	Must have	Must have	Could have	Should have	Must have
VDS	6	Aggregate patient data visualisation	The system shall permit to visualise aggregates of patient data in the visualisation dashboard	Yes	Scientist/ Clinician	T6.2	Must have	Must have	Must have	Could have	Must have	Should have	Must have
VDS	7	Time-Series Analysis output	The system shall display the results of time series analysis.	Yes	Scientist/ Clinician	T6.2	Must have	Should have	Must have	Should have	Must have	Should have	Must have

		visualisation											
VDS	8	Data manipulation plug-ins	The system shall allow scientists to install plug-ins that would provide black box functionalities offered by the community.	Yes	Scientist/ Clinician	T6.2	Would be nice		Would be nice	Must have	Should have	Should have	Would be nice

4.3.19 INTEGRATED SOLUTION REQUIREMENTS

Table 45: Integrated Solution Requirements

Code	No	Title	Description	User facing? (Yes/ No)	User role(s)	Task	Technical Partners Priority	NIA Priority	UU Priority	IR-HSCSP Priority	KCL Priority	UEDIN Priority	CHS-RMC Priority
INS	1	Modularity	The system shall be a modular integrated solution (including security and data ingestion tools from WP5) built on three architectural layers: Data Lake, Data analysis and Data Presentation.	No	None	T7.3	Should have						
INS	2	3-layer architecture	The system architecture will be built upon three architectural layers, namely the Data Lake, responsible for channelling data sources upstream into the Data analysis layer, where the data mining and Machine Learning techniques are used to deliver added value insight and analysis, and the Data Presentation layer, which is the first and foremost module used by users and stakeholders, willing to operatively access the MES-CoBraD services.	No	None	T7.3	Should have						

4.4 NON-FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

This section aims to collect the non-functional requirements (NFR) that the system should meet. Whereas functional requirements define what a system should do, non-functional requirements specify how the system must work.

Moreover, non-functional requirements are those characteristics which describe how the system should behave and the potential constraints upon the system behaviour. Table 46 below presents all non-functional requirements grouped in 3 categories:

1. GUI – Graphical User Interface Requirements
2. INT – Interoperability Requirements
3. SYS – System Requirements

Table 46: Non-functional requirements

Id	Category	Description	Priority
GUI	Graphical User Interface Requirements		
GUI-001	Provide common look-and-feel to the graphical user interface	MES-CoBraD must provide a common look-and-feel through a portal-like user interface to guide the user to the underlying functionality of the internal components such as a portal-like approach, which is common practice for integrating distinct functional components and providing an integrated presentation layer.	High
GUI-002	Provide intuitive general navigation methods	MES-CoBraD must provide intuitive general navigation methods. At least two of the following navigation methods should be provided: main menu, site map, and search engine. Breadcrumbs must be used to indicate the current feature and to provide easy hierarchical navigation.	High
GUI-003	Use clear and unambiguous text to describe features	Text used for the MES-CoBraD' user interface should be clear and unambiguous. Typefaces and fonts used should be easily readable and should support international accents. Where symbols are used consider associating descriptive text as well. Beware of cultural differences related to naming and symbols.	High
GUI-004	Support localised texts for international end-users	MES-CoBraD must support localised texts for international end-users, by using Unicode compliance for global text display, independent from a specific language/character set encoding, while also supporting right-to-left languages.	High
GUI-005	Use appropriate colours and	MES-CoBraD must use appropriate	Medium

	contrast	colours and contrast, avoiding conveying meaning by colour, as there may be cultural differences in interpreting colours between users of the system, while making sure that information is comprehensible, even if the colours are absent.	
GUI-006	Provide consistent labels for buttons and fields	MES-CoBraD must provide consistent labels for buttons and fields. An explicit label must be provided for each form field. Each label must be placed close to the field to which it is attached. Group together related fields. Clearly indicate mandatory fields and provide help for entering data.	Medium
GUI-007	Indicate the size and format of documents available for download	MES-CoBraD must indicate the size and format of each document that can be downloaded. For each link that points to a document that can be downloaded, link text should include the document name, file format and size.	Medium
GUI-008	Provide account authentication interface for user identification	MES-CoBraD must provide a graphical interface for authenticating end-users. The interface should also allow system administrators to create user accounts, to configure appropriate roles and permissions authorisations, to activate and deactivate accounts, and to configure password reset intervals	High
GUI-009	Provide adaptive user interface based on authorisation access rights	MES-CoBraD must provide adaptive user interface based on authorisation access rights of the user, such as displaying only links/menus to activities and resources that the user has access to.	High
INT	Interoperability Requirements		
INT-001	Integrate components and external systems in a loosely coupled way	MES-CoBraD must integrate internal components and external systems in a loosely coupled way; as such that each of its components has, or makes use of, little or no knowledge of the definitions of other separate components.	High
INT-002	System components expose and consume data in standardised way	MES-CoBraD components must expose and consume data in standardised way.	High
INT-003	Publish and describe exposed interfaces towards other systems	MES-CoBraD must publish and describe exposed interfaces towards other systems by managing a set of open APIs towards other systems, used both to develop the actual MES-CoBraD system and to extend the	High

		system in the future if needed.	
INT-004	Describe the syntax and format used for data exchange messages	MES-CoBraD must describe the syntax and format used for data exchange messages, while also specifying the semantics of data fields. Standardisation of messages ensures that messages are robust, interoperable and reusable.	High
INT-005	Leverage open standards to communicate with external systems	MES-CoBraD must leverage open standards, where available, to communicate with external systems, as opposed to implementing custom means of data exchange.	Medium
SYS	System Requirements		
SYS-001	Support high-availability requirements	MES-CoBraD must support high-availability requirements, operating without outages within certain periods, but still allowing for scheduled maintenance downtimes outside of committed hours.	High
SYS-002	Support backup and recovery operations	MES-CoBraD must support copying and archiving data for restoring the original after a data loss event.	High
SYS-003	Support both horizontal and vertical scalability scenarios	MES-CoBraD must support both horizontal and vertical scalability for capacity expansion scenarios.	High
SYS-004	Support agreed workload and response time performance requirements	MES-CoBraD must support agreed workload and response time performance requirements guaranteeing operation within considered time limits.	High
SYS-005	Support agreed performance requirements with minimal hardware	MES-CoBraD must support agreed performance requirements guaranteeing operation at considered peak workload with minimal hardware configuration.	High
SYS-006	Allow working on different hardware platforms (x64 compatible)	MES-CoBraD must be designed to allow running server-side services on different hardware platforms (x64 compatible).	High
SYS-007	Support virtualisation options for hardware resources	MES-CoBraD must support virtualisation options for hardware resources to allow optimal use of existing capacity, within budget constraints.	High

5 HIGH-LEVEL ARCHITECTURE

5.1 OVERVIEW

In this chapter we are presenting the architecture of MES-CoBraD from a software development perspective. We are following the methodological approach more broadly described in Chapter 2 and more specifically in Section 2.5 Based on the methodology used, we are presenting seven architectural views: Use Case, Functional (Logical), Development, Deployment (Physical), Information, Integration and Security.

5.1.1 ARCHITECTURAL VIEWS

The integrated view of the proposed MES-CoBraD architecture is based on two reference architectural perspectives: 4+x and the business layered architecture.

Figure 6 depicts the architectural perspectives proposed in close connection with business layer.

Figure 6. MES-CoBraD architecture design

In the following subsections the tools are surveyed and positioned based on their features and proposed functionalities for MES-CoBraD value chain and mapped on the views described in the previous section (Figure 6).

5.1.2 TOOLS

The tools used are listed in Chapter 4, Table 24 at page 53.

6 ARCHITECTURAL VIEW MODEL

This chapter is a detailed presentation of the seven views referred by the methodology chosen. For each view, a diagram and an explanation of the containing elements are included.

6.1 USE CASE VIEW

Considering the architectural perspectives proposed in close connection with layer organisation, the use case view is a central cross layer perspective about the project.

The use case view is organised to express what the DoA presents as expected PUCs i.e.:

- › PUC 1: MES-CoBraD Multidisciplinary Multisource Real-World Data Assessment Protocol
- › PUC 2: MES-CoBraD Advanced Analytics Deep-Phenotyping and Prognostication
- › PUC3: MES-CoBraD Real-World Therapy Repurposing and Approved Indication Reassessment
- › PUC4: Development and Validation of a multidisciplinary expert system for the assessment and management of complex brain disorders – MES-CoBraD”

The first Pilot Use Case (PUC 1) propose the comprehensive assessment of CoBraD through a novel clinical multidisciplinary multisource diagnostic protocol that relies on optimising real-world practices, by integrating several modalities of Real-World Data and their Metadata, allowing for deep phenotyping of people with NCD, epilepsy and sleep disorders, and assessment of their comorbidities, towards achieving precision and personalised medicine goals (see DoA).

The second Pilot Use case (PUC 2) will conduct a comprehensive multidisciplinary analysis of big, interrelated data represented into clinically and socially relevant evidence-based outcomes.

The third Pilot Use Case (PUC 3) will address therapeutic clinical and research challenges, including suboptimal or contraindicated therapies, need for effective treatments, assessment of psychosocial impact of therapies, patient access to healthcare and compliance, monitoring of approved therapies in real-world practice, and multiple failed costly clinical trials, through research protocols combining scientific expertise and resources

The fourth Pilot Use Case (PUC 4) has as main objective the Development and Validation of a multidisciplinary expert system. Expert System in medical science is a decision-making algorithm to achieve a medically relevant goal (diagnostic or therapeutic), mimicking or, ideally, surpassing a human expert.

Based on the target of each use case we have identified the following actors:

- › Patients
- › Caregivers
- › Clinicians
- › Scientific community
- › Pharma and Medical Informatics Industry
- › Government Stakeholders
- › System administrators
- › Security engineers
- › Developers

- › Public

For each of the aforementioned actors we have identified the following use cases:

6.1.1 PATIENTS USE CASES

- › Give access to their data about the diseases (PUC 1)
- › Register the results after the application of protocols (PUC 1)

6.1.2 CAREGIVERS USE CASES

- › Facilitate access to patient data (PUC 1)
- › Supervise the application of protocols (PUC 1, PUC 3)

6.1.3 CLINICIANS USE CASES

- › Be informed about new protocols (PUC 1)
- › Asses the protocols in real world (PUC 1)
- › Diagnosis based on collected multidisciplinary information (PUC 1)
- › Improve the diagnosis based on Advanced Analytics (PUC 2)
- › Assess and validate Data Analytics results (PUC 2)
- › Identification of possible repurposing and efficacy concerns of established real-world therapies (PUC 3)
- › Assess and validate Expert System results (PUC 4)

6.1.4 SCIENTIST USE CASES

- › Use the acquired knowledge (PUC 1)
- › Create and disseminate new knowledge (PUC 1, PUC 2, PUC 3, and PUC 4)
- › Elaborate and disseminate complex studies (PUC 1, PUC 2, PUC 3, and PUC 4)
- › Use Data Analytics to create accurate studies (PUC 2)
- › Use the models created for other domains (PUC 4)

6.1.5 SYSTEM ADMINISTRATOR USE CASES

- › Configure systems (PUC 1, PUC 2, PUC 3, and PUC 4)
- › Monitor the system (PUC 1, PUC 2, PUC 3, and PUC 4)
- › Create reports (PUC 1, PUC 2, PUC 3, and PUC 4)

6.1.6 SECURITY ENGINEERS USE CASES

- › Define the policies for data access (PUC 1, PUC 2, PUC 3, and PUC 4)
- › Supervise the system from security perspective (PUC 1, PUC 2, PUC 3, and PUC 4)
- › Create and administer users and roles (PUC 1, PUC 2, PUC 3, and PUC 4)

6.1.7 DEVELOPERS USE CASES

- › Implement and deploy data collection mechanisms (PUC 1)
- › Implement and deploy new models (PUC 1, PUC 3, PUC 4)
- › Check the accuracy of the results of the new models (PUC 3, PUC 4)

6.1.8 INDUSTRY USE CASES

- › Use the research results for the creation of specific outcomes. (PUC 1, PUC 2, PUC 3, and PUC 4)
- › Collect the results on the usage of a specific medication or protocol (PUC 3)

6.1.9 GOVERNMENT USE CASES

- › Define healthcare policy
- › Use research results when voting decisions around health

6.1.10 PUBLIC USE CASES

- › Being informed about research results in healthcare system

6.2 FUNCTION VIEW (LOGICAL VIEW)

The functional view expresses how the architecture is serving the functional requirements of the system. As a global functional perspective, the tools used in this project are serving a global system as that presented in Figure 7. MES-CoBraD Logical architecture below.

In the Function view we are distinguishing the following major blocks:

Data sources, presented in the blocks are the left of the diagram. They are components located in clinics, at patients, or external data providers. Data collection is managed by edge plugins. The data is also anonymised and next is ingested in the Data Lake component.

Security and Anonymisation framework, presented at the right of data sources, is responsible for the anonymisation of data, and also for all the secured access to the system.

Data lake, presented in the block at the bottom of the diagram. This is the place where all data is

persisted. The data is then shared to the central processing unit.

Communication Bus is responsible for data exchange between the system components. The communication is mainly synchronous and is based on Remote Procedure Call or REST API.

Process management Systems is the central processing system, represented in the centre of the diagram. It refers to the Expert Systems, linked with Query Builder, Data Analytics, Adaptive Training and Data Visualisations.

Platform is the component depicted in the centre of the diagram, on top of process management system. It hosts the whole system management components, including Query management, variable management, protocols management. It also includes the edge plug-in showcase

Data presentation (frontends) is depicted in the top part of the diagram and contains the user interface used by the actors working with the system. The UI can be WEB (browser), mobile, or Desktop clients.

Infrastructure. Is the basement for the whole system. It has all the hardware components and the supporting software components (OS, libraries, tools, etc.)

Figure 7. MES-CoBraD Logical architecture

6.3 DEVELOPMENT VIEW

The development view details the architecture that supports the development process. It provides a

programmer’s perspective on the system and relies on software management. This view is mainly used to describe the modules of the system [Figure 8].

Within MES-CoBraD project different layers will be approached as part of this view. The development infrastructure is addressed in terms of development environment while the component layer focuses on the integration readiness and hardware dependencies.

The technologies used to create the component are presented with both software and hardware details.

Hardware components represent the physical layer of the development platform in term of servers used for development, including source and artifact repositories like SVN, Git, Gitlab or Docker repository, and other hardware components relevant to the project such as laptops or desktops, mobiles or other specific devices like IoT.

Software components represent the logical layer of the development view comprised of:

- › Operating System: Linux, Windows, MacOS.
- › Databases and databases tools: PostgreSQL and PgAdmin, MySQL etc.
- › NoSQL systems: MongoDB and Compass, Cassandra, etc.
- › IDEs: Netbeans, Microsoft Dev Studio, IntelliJ Idea, Eclipse, etc.
- › Programming languages: Python, Java, Golang, .NET, C++, etc.
- › APIs: AWS, others.

6.3.1 ELICITED INFORMATION FROM TECHNOLOGY PROVIDERS

Each technology provider shared details about the tool deployed in MES-CoBraD via the Technologies and Capabilities Template described in Section 2.4.2 above and the results of which are presented in Chapter 3.

6.3.2 MES-COBRA D TOOLS CROSS-ANALYSIS

From development point of view MES-CoBraD tools engage a wide range of technologies collected from tools providers, and summarised in Table 47, below:

Table 47. Development tools and technologies used by MES-CoBraD tool providers

Category	Tools and technologies
Operating Systems	Ubuntu Linux, RHEL, Windows, Linux
Containers	Docker, Swarm
Tools, libraries	OpenCV, Scikit, pandas, flask, VTK, MiniO Data Mashup Editor Digital Enabler
Data storage	Datalake, hosted in cloud, AWS S3 compatible
IDEs	Python 3.7, Netbeans, Microsoft Dev Studio, IntelliJ Idea
Programming languages:	Python 3.7, Django 3.0.2, React, Java 1.11,
APIs	Spring REST API, JAX-RS (Jersey) REST API Elastic Search
User interface	JS/React, Django, Bootstrap, Javascript, PHP, Kibana
CI/CD tools;	Cloud based Git Repository, Git Actions, Git Packages
Licence	proprietary, MIT licence, Windows, open source
Exposed services	REST API, JSON, syslog reports/API endpoints, charts, dashboards
Hardware dependencies	SIM card, industrial components,
Hardware components	Servers

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Desktop computersLaptopsMobilesSpecial devicesData acquisition devicesNetwork (Wi-Fi, Ethernet)
--	--

The information collected from technology providers reveals a complex landscape of tools and technologies. With such a complex input the overall system design will have to overcome design challenges in order to provide a unified toolkit.

The main diagram for the development view is depicted in Figure 8:

Figure 8. MES-CoBraD development model

6.4 DEPLOYMENT VIEW

The deployment view describes aspects necessary to go into live operation. It provides a system engineer’s perspective on the system and relies on hardware and software environment to run on field. The deployment view accommodates all the components described in the development view in a unitary system. Therefore, complex runtime dependencies runtime environments and situations where the system may be deployed in a number of several environments with different characteristics might apply (see Figure 9).

Basically, in this environment all the software and hardware components will be detailed, while some minor changes at runtime might occur.

6.4.1.1 Elicited information from technology providers

The technologies and tools used by the runtime system are those presented in the development view plus specific deployment architecture:

Presence in cloud. It refers to functionality available in cloud and called by other components.

Containerisation. Containers allow packaging of an application and its dependencies together into one artifact that can be version controlled and allowing easy replication of the application across many deployment environments. This approach reduces the number of resources needed as each container only holds the application and its related binaries or libraries.

Virtualisation. A virtual machine performs an emulation of a computer system that runs applications and programs like a separate computer.

APIs exposure. API is an interface that facilitates the integration between multiple software components by defining function calls.

Assets and technologies refer to the tools used by each component (commercial or open source, libraries, environments, etc)

Each technology provider shared details about the tools used in MES-CoBraD, as displayed in Table 48.

Table 48. Deployment view template

Tool	Description
Is the application dockerisable?	<Yes/No>
Is the application in cloud?	<Yes/No>
Virtual Machine?	<Please specify if this is the case / the OS version and number and other relevant details>
APIs	<please provide details about what services could be exposed for integration purpose>
Assets/technologies	<please provide details about all the technologies used, such as: server, back-end, specific technologies>

Based on the information collected the tools developed as part of this project are as presented in the table below:

Table 49. Deployment view consolidated info

Tool	Cloud	Is docker	VM	APIs	Technologies, tools
Data Analytics	No	possible	no	yes	Python 3.6+, FastAPI
Data Visualiser	No	possible	no	yes	Python 3.6+, FastAPI, AmCharts, Nilearn, Visbrain and MNE-Python
Query Builder	No	possible	no	yes	Python 3.6+, FastAPI
Data Lake	Yes	no	no	yes	MinIO, AWS S3, MongoDB, PostgreSQL, InfluxDB, Graylog
Data Harmonisation Module					Data Mashup Editor, MQTT, Kafka
Data Ingestion Module					Apache Airflow
Expert System					Python 3.6+,
Artificial Intelligence					Django, TensorFlow, PyTorch, Keras, Alibi Explain, Captum
Platform	No	No	VM	yes	Linux, Java, Tomcat, Spring Boot, Primefaces, Keycloak, Kafka

The deployment model proposed is presented in the figure below:

Figure 9. MES-CoBrad deployment model

6.5 INFORMATION VIEW

It will present the data and the flow of data in the system. The content of this view will follow the structure:

- > Data inputs (data model, data format)
- > Data outputs (data model, data format)
- > Entity relationship diagram (ERD)

Using the survey presented in Table 50, each technology provider filled in the relevant details about own tool.

Table 50. Information view

Tool	Description
Inputs	<i>please specify the inputs necessary for the module</i>
Data model	<i>please specify if you use a standard data model or a custom</i>
Format	<i>please provide details about the data format e.g. XML, CSV</i>
Outputs	<i>please provide the outputs (features) that the module will provide</i>
Data model	<i>please specify if you use a standard data model or a custom</i>
Format	<i>please provide details about the data format e.g. XML, CSV</i>
ERD	<i>please provide the entity relationship diagram</i>

Based on the information received, we are able to consolidate this view in the next table

Table 51. Information view consolidated info

Tool	Input	Output	Format	Technologies, tools
Data Analytics				
Data Visualiser				
Query Builder				
Data Lake				AWS S3
Data Harmonization Module				
Data Ingestion Module				
Expert System				
Artificial Intelligence				
Platform				

6.6 SECURITY VIEW

The security view presents the characteristics of the system in terms of confidentiality, integrity and availability. This is recognised as CIA Triad in information security (Seker, 2020)

The CIA Triad is a central part of ISO/IEC 27001:2019, the international standard that describes best practice for an information security management system.

Figure 10. CIA Triad | Source: (Seker, 2020)

The overall security takes into consideration the well-established CIA triad. The CIA triad (Figure 10) is a well-known concept in security that defines the security of a system. Some people define the CIA triad as the three pillars of security, all equally important.

Confidentiality. This pillar assures that the information in a computer system can be only accessed by the people that should view it. Confidentiality can be achieved through using all the methods described below (they should be used together).

Authentication – an application should use unique named accounts that authenticate a user based on at least one authentication factor. The user account should be named and should uniquely identify that user. Anonymous accounts like *root* should be disabled, because if more people have access to the password there won't be a trail of who did what. Authentication can be done using one or more factors. A user can be authenticated in system based on:

What he knows – a password

What he has – a token or a key card

What he is – biometrics (fingerprint, iris, etc.)

Authorisation – after a user is authenticated the system must define what can the user do, what the user is authorised to do. This authorisation is maintained through access rights. Access rights will follow the least privilege principle. A user is given only the access necessary to do his job.

Encryption – this method is used to make sure the data is safe from prying eyes Encryption is a two-way mathematical function that allows the data to be rendered unreadable for the people without the decryption key. Encryption should be used for both data at rest (stored) or data in transit (data transmitted over the internet). The two methods explained above can't be implemented if encryption is not used. For example: if we try authentication someone by sent the password unencrypted over the internet the entire system will be compromised, because if the password is compromised that user account will be compromised.

Integrity. This pillar assures that data is accurate and trustworthy. We need to know that the data we are viewing or modifying is the actual data from the system. The same principle applies in reverse, we need

to make sure that the data we send to the server is the data we modified. Integrity is assured using:

encryption – we make sure that the data we transmit over the internet is encrypted and can't be read or modified by other people.

hashing - this method assures the integrity of data per se but can't work without other methods presented here. Hashing is a mathematical collusion resistant one-way function that presents a digest of a message. If the message is changed that digest is changed. A property of a hash algorithm is that any small change in the initial message will produce a major change in the hash. Integrity is an innate property of Public Key Infrastructure (PKI), digital certificates, that we'll be used throughout the project.

Authentication and authorisation are also used here, because only an authenticated user should be able to access the system, and the system should be accessed based on the user rights.

Availability. This pillar assures that the system is accessible for the people that need access to it for as much time as possible. It doesn't matter how secure a system is if you can't have access to it, the system doesn't work.

Availability is achieved by putting in place redundancies both for:

Capacity – assuring that the right number of concurrent users can use the system-of-systems

Protection against DDoS – protection against malicious actors that might want to flood it with unnecessary requests to make it unavailable.

Backups – system backups are very important because if a breach occurs and all the historic data is deleted/encrypted by ransomware the system becomes unavailable.

Logs – logs are applicable for the system as whole, not only in the availability part. We mention it here because it's an integral part of business continuity. Logs allow system administrators to monitor what's happening in real time or what has happened at a point in time.

6.6.1 SECURITY REQUIREMENTS

Table 52: Security requirements

Id	Category	Description
COM-001	User Traffic	MES-CoBraD must encrypt all communications between a user of the system. All web pages must be served over HTTPS.
COM-002	Module Traffic	All communications between modules must be encrypted. The use of TLS is recommended for HTTP based communications. All external communication must be conducted over HTTPS.
COM-003	Sensor Traffic	All communications to external devices and services must be encrypted. The use of TLS is recommended for HTTP based communications.
COM-004	Message Passing	All messages passed to and from the MES-CoBraD message bus must be encrypted. Messages passed must avoid sending identifying information.
COM-005	Entry points	All entry points to the MES-CoBraD system must be restricted in what functionality they expose. An endpoint should only expose the data that is needed.
COM-006	Data Authenticity	All data contained with the MES-CoBraD system must be accompanied with a cryptographic signature. The originating module must sign the data with the modules own private key. Where modules receive data from other modules, they must check the signature against the sending module's private key and the data.
COM-007	Data Sanitisation	All modules in the MES-CoBraD system must perform a basic level of input sanitisation, e.g. validating against a set data model or standard,

		<p>such as JavaScript Object Notation (JSON). Where a standard structure is not defined, properties such as file size may be used to validate instead.</p> <p>A common attack vector is via injection, where raw queries/commands can be executed. All modules must not allow raw queries to be executed.</p>
COM-008	Rate Limiting	Modules with exposed endpoints must implement rate limiting as protection against Denial of Service (DoS) caused by external attackers or malfunctioning modules.
Authentication		
AUTH-001	Internal Login	The MES-CoBraD system must provide an interface to those users who are internal to the system. This interface must not be publicly accessible.
AUTH-002	External Login	The MES-CoBraD system must provide an interface to those users who are external ('guests') to the system in order to authenticate themselves with the system. When users are authenticated with this interface, they should have restricted access to functionality and data. These restrictions should be configurable by access controls.
AUTH-003	Device Authentication	All devices must authenticate with the MES-CoBraD system and modules using JWT tokens where possible.
AUTH-004	Token Lifespan	All authentication tokens must have a finite lifespan. A recommended expiration period is 30 days.
AUTH-005	Token Revocation	The MES-CoBraD system must have a centralised system to create, revoke and invalidate any tokens.
Logging		
LOG-001	Contents	<p>Modules in production must not log any stack traces, domain data or, any other kind of information that may indicate how the module operates or what data it is currently processing.</p> <p>Log contents must be concise and only expose what is needed for debugging purposes.</p>
LOG-001	Log Storage	The MES-CoBraD system must provide a secure centralised location for the storage of logs from the system and individual modules. Modules are also responsible for providing secure storage for their own logs outside of the centralised system.
LOG-002	Log Accessibility	The MES-CoBraD system must provide a method, such as a Graphical User Interface (GUI), that is accessible to the system administrators by which to view the logs of the system.
LOG-003	User Events	Each module must record any user events, such as user creation, password changes, new logins and failed logins.
LOG-004	Network Events	Each module must record any network related events such as new connections, connection failures.
LOG-005	Authentication Events	Each module must record any authentication success/failures; these include authentication events with accessing other modules and accesses from other modules.
LOG-006	Messages	Modules must keep logs of received events from the MES-CoBraD message hub. Including the topic and the originating module.
LOG-007	Data Events	<p>Modules must keep logs of modifications to data, data validation errors and data verification errors.</p> <p>Modules must record CRUD operations performed on data, including the originating module.</p>
Data Storage and Caching		
DS-001	Data Encryption	All data stored within the MES-CoBraD system must be encrypted where possible. This includes and temporary data stores and caches.

DS-002	Data Lifetime	All data stored must be kept for a finite lifetime. When stored/cached data is no longer needed it must be securely deleted from data stores/caches.
DS-003	Key Store	Each module must incorporate a secure key storage system to hold any private keys, such as API keys, keys used for signing data and keys/tokens for authenticating with modules and services.
DS-004	Key Management	The MES-CoBraD system must have the ability to create, revoke and invalidate any keys stored.
Access Control		
AC-001	Hierarchy of Access	The MES-CoBraD system must provide a system by which features and data can be restricted based on a role hierarchy (for example the 'admin' role grants the ability to edit system settings while a 'user' role would not). Access controls will be facilitated through
AC-002	Data Access Restrictions	Users of the system must be restricted to what data they can access based on role. Users should be restricted on a case level as well as by specific type of data. These access controls should be configurable base on the hierarchical role system.
AC-003	Physical Restrictions	The MES-CoBraD system must have the ability to restrict access and functionality based on identifying features of a user's computer. This can be features such as IP address and MAC addresses.

6.6.2 SECURITY VIEW FROM TECHNOLOGY PROVIDERS

We have used Table 53 to collect relevant information from technology providers in terms of security capabilities. Details on both technical aspects and organisational measures were elicited from each tool. The responses per each tool are included in Annex 4.2 Architectural views.

Table 53. Security view survey

Tool	Description
Authentication / Authorisation	<please describe the authentication and authorisation process>
Encryption	<please specify encryption type and implementation>
Applicable standards	<specify applicable standards, if any>

6.6.3 MES-CoBRAD TOOLS CROSS-ANALYSIS

A summary of the security measures provisioned by technology providers is presented in Table 54.

Table 54. Tools-summary

Tool	Description
Authentication / Authorisation	All modules will authenticate based on username and password either in a web form or using API, depending on the module.
Encryption	All communication between the front-end user interface and the backend is protected by HTTPS. For the project we'll use free Certificate Authority (Let's Encrypt) that will generate certificates.
Applicable standards	ISO 27001, X.509 public key certificates

The view is presented separately on each layer:

Component: Every system component works both as a standalone component and an integrated system.

Communication: All communication will be encrypted using asymmetric encryption. We'll use standard PKI implementation. We'll use free Let's Encrypt CA to issue certificates to all parties involved. The web servers will be configured to use HTTPS protocol.

Information: All information is stored into databases. Communication between modules is done in a secure fashion using encrypted communication implemented using standard PKI. PKI through asymmetric encryption assures both data confidentiality and integrity. The technologies used for communication are REST/API.

Function & Business: Access to the system is allowed only https or other secure protocols, as explained in the communication layer. After authentication a token will be stored on the client that will be used for authorisation in other services using REST APIs. The system will encrypt all data using asymmetric cryptography

Database constraints are defined to allow integrity and coherence of data with planned back-ups.

6.7 INTEGRATION VIEW

Considering the architectural perspectives proposed in close connection with layer the integration view is a composed of the pillars supporting all the layers.

The MES-CoBraD project develops an integrated system covering the complete value chain. The construction of this toolkit is following the steps:

- › Create an optimised framework
- › Place all the tools in the framework
- › Place Edge plug-ins on client systems

Open standards and protocols are used for all components placed in the system both in terms of development and ease of use.

The General common component refers to:

Basement hardware shelf. Contains power supplies, cables, measurement units.

Basement software shelf: It contains the Operating system, Java Runtime and virtualisation mechanism, serving all the software components. In our case it is Linux running VMware system and running Java 1.8 and JEE

Container Manager: It is a software component. It run a container engine (Docker), where all Docker images can be run

Communication HUB: It is a software component. It runs a message broker (Kafka) and communication bus for REST services.

Persistence: There are software components used for data persistence. They can be RDBMS (Postgres) databases and NoSQL (Cassandra)

Application servers. They are software components (WEB App server like Apache Tomcat)

Presentation tools. They are software tools used to display data in a format required by end users. Kibana is one example.

The **specific components** that are covering the functionalities are placed on:

- › Virtual machines (software components)
- › Docker images (software components)
- › Standalone applications (software components)
- › Message producers (communication ports)
- › Message consumers (communication ports)
- › REST Clients (communication ports)
- › REST APIs (communication ports)
- › Hardware components

Considering the particularities of the proposed architecture alongside with the deployed tools and technologies, MES-CoBraD integration approach builds upon technology-oriented pillars supporting architectural layers.

7 DETAILED LAYERED ARCHITECTURE

7.1 OVERVIEW

Considering the methodology presented in Chapter 2, we are focusing now on describing the architectural elements of the five layers mentioned previously and figured out in Figure 6. MES-CoBraD architecture design at page 87.

7.2 APPROACH

Our approach is to identify the components on each layer and to present them on that layer. If a component is shared among many layers, it will be described each time with the role having on that layer. The presentation will follow a correlation between the technical aspects and the business aspects of the components.

Data Analytics

- Data Visualiser
- Query Builder
- Data Lake
- Data Harmonisation Module
- Data Ingestion Module
- Expert System
- Artificial Intelligence
- Platform

7.3 COMPONENT LAYER

We are presenting in this chapter the components of the system, as they are producing and delivering by the technologies provider. We focus on the structure and the role of components.

We have a system of systems, deployed in cloud, on user premises, and centrally on the project platform.

7.3.1 CLOUD COMPONENTS

The cloud components used are for data storage, we have a data lake responsible for this and described below.

7.3.2 DATA LAKE

The MES-CoBraD Data Lake is a multi-technology storage layer that is able to store several types of data collected in the system. It encompasses different technological stacks, that are used according to the specific data processing needs. The main backbone of the component is the Digital Enabler's "Data Storage". It is an Object Storage based on MinIO (<https://min.io>) opensource technology. It allows to store different kinds of data, regardless their structure and format, within the so-called *buckets*, i.e. within a box that can contain several GB (and even TB) of heterogeneous data in order to make them consumable from other systems.

The Object Storage, nevertheless, is not the only module of the Data Lake component. As mentioned above, according to the specific data elaboration planned for each data type, the Data Lake is able to store data also in the following types of databases:

- › MongoDB (<https://www.mongodb.com>): Document oriented No-SQL database

- › PostgreSQL (<https://www.postgresql.org>): Relational database
- › InfluxDB (<https://www.influxdata.com>): TimeSeries DB
- › Graylog (<https://www.graylog.org>): Log server

Thanks to this multi-technological approach, the MES-CoBraD Data Lake enables several different types of data processing scenarios, both for data analysis, elaboration and visualisation purposes.

7.3.3 COMMON INFRASTRUCTURE

The project common infrastructure is the central part of the hole system and has the hardware and software elements able to host and orchestrate the whole system. We are describing it as the MES-CoBraD Plaform.

7.3.3.1 Hardware Platform

The platform proposes two environments:

- › Development and test environment
- › Production environment

The current document refers to the development and test environment. The production environment will be delivered by the end of the project, it will be mainly similar with development and test, and will incorporate the adjustments considered as necessary after the whole test process.

The development environment follows the physical architecture presented before as deployment model.

There are 7 Virtual Machines, hosted by VMWare², identified with the numbers in parenthesis, with the following hardware capabilities:

Table 55: Virtual Machines Hardware Capabilities

Servers	Id. No.	# CPUs	RAM
Proxy Server	114	2	16GB
Communication Server	116	4	16GB
Cluster Master Node	115	4	16GB
Cluster Child Nodes	117, 118, 119	6	32GB
Main Portal	120	12	48GB

² <https://www.vmware.com/>


```

simavi@mescobrasd-revproxy: ~
  1  [|          0.7%]   Tasks: 33, 35 thr; 1 running
  2  [           0.0%]   Load average: 0.00 0.00 0.00
Mem[|||||||||] 229M/15.6G] Uptime: 55 days, 01:56:48
Swp[           0K/4.00G]

  PID USER      PRI  NI  VIRT   RES   SHR  S  CPU% MEM%   TIME+  Command
2074237 simavi    20   0   7924   3840  3220  R   1.3  0.0   0:00.08 htop
   660 root      RT    0   337M  18224  8300  S   0.7  0.1  57:05.80 /sbin/multipath
1615356 root      19  -1   294M   135M  134M  S   0.0  0.8   5:58.95 /lib/systemd/sy
   1 root      20   0   164M  12868  8260  S   0.0  0.1   1:03.72 /lib/systemd/sy
  
```

Figure 11 – Proxy server

```

simavi@mescobrasd-cd: ~
  1  [|          0.7%]   Tasks: 44, 309 thr; 1 running
  2  [           0.0%]   Load average: 0.00 0.00 0.00
  3  [|          2.0%]   Uptime: 54 days, 23:03:43
  4  [           0.0%]
Mem[|||||||||] 2.47G/15.6G]
Swp[           0K/4.00G]

  PID USER      PRI  NI  VIRT   RES   SHR  S  CPU% MEM%   TIME+  Command
2085598 simavi    20   0   8584   4612  3356  R   2.0  0.0   0:00.12 htop
  101288 eng       20   0  4650M   944M  19536  S   0.7  5.9  8h22:26 /opt/bitnami/ja
  101879 eng       20   0  4650M   944M  19536  S   0.7  5.9  18:09.48 /opt/bitnami/ja
  101114 eng       20   0  4600M   714M  18660  S   0.0  4.5  2h45:51 java -Dzookeeper
  
```

Figure 12 – Communication server

```

simavi@mescibrasd-ci: ~
  1  [           0.0%]   Tasks: 33, 60 thr; 1 running
  2  [           0.0%]   Load average: 0.07 0.02 0.00
  3  [|          2.0%]   Uptime: 55 days, 01:50:57
  4  [           0.0%]
Mem[|||||||||] 313M/15.6G]
Swp[           0K/4.00G]

  PID USER      PRI  NI  VIRT   RES   SHR  S  CPU% MEM%   TIME+  Command
2094051 simavi    20   0   7932   3972  3340  R   0.7  0.0   0:00.08 htop
   8045 root      20   0   231M   8116   6648  S   0.7  0.0  1h33:43 /usr/bin/vmtool
  26467 root      20   0  1530M  44036  29584  S   0.0  0.3  2h31:12 /usr/bin/contai
  
```

Figure 13 – Cluster master server


```

simavi@mescobrasd-kub1: ~
1  [          0.0%]  4  [||]          1.3%]
2  [          0.0%]  5  [          0.0%]
3  [          0.0%]  6  [|]          0.7%]
Mem[|||||]          692M/31.4G]  Tasks: 36, 151 thr; 1 running
Swp[          0K/8.00G]  Load average: 0.01 0.01 0.00
                          Uptime: 54 days, 23:14:41

  PID USER      PRI  NI  VIRT   RES   SHR  S  CPU% MEM%   TIME+  Command
3710738 simavi    20   0  8112  4056  3220  R   1.3  0.0  0:00.10 htop
 95232 root      20   0 1786M  121M 59268  S   1.3  0.4  3h26:50 /usr/bin/docker
 95208 root      20   0 1786M  121M 59268  S   0.7  0.4 12h10:04 /usr/bin/docker
116301 iacobc   20   0 1583M  322M 29152  S   0.7  1.0  1h20:11 /usr/lib/jvm/ja
116285 iacobc   20   0 1583M  322M 29152  S   0.7  1.0  2h01:36 /usr/lib/jvm/ja

```

Figure 14 – Cluster child servers

```

simavi@mescobrasd-app: ~
1  [          0.0%]  4  [          0.0%]  7  [          0.0%]  10 [          0.0%]
2  [|]          0.7%]  5  [          0.0%]  8  [          0.0%]  11 [|]          0.7%]
3  [          0.0%]  6  [          0.0%]  9  [          0.0%]  12 [          0.0%]
Mem[|||||]          1.25G/47.1G]  Tasks: 49, 211 thr; 1 running
Swp[          0K/8.00G]  Load average: 0.00 0.01 0.00
                          Uptime: 54 days, 22:53:21

  PID USER      PRI  NI  VIRT   RES   SHR  S  CPU% MEM%   TIME+  Command
2396768 simavi    20   0  8624  4420  3628  R   1.3  0.0  0:00.18 htop
 90450 tomcat    20   0 16.5G  759M 36936  S   0.7  1.6  2h51:59 /usr/lib/jvm/de
 91089 472      20   0  779M  82908 54932  S   0.0  0.2  5:59.99 grafana-server
   873 root      20   0  231M  8288  6720  S   0.0  0.0  1h34:10 /usr/bin/vmtool
 90469 tomcat    20   0 16.5G  759M 36936  S   0.0  1.6  1h16:28 /usr/lib/jvm/de

```

Figure 15 – Main portal server

7.3.3.2 Software platform

Operating System

```

Chassis:          vm
Machine ID:      623ac72df336484490fdc62c64c35fe2
Boot ID:         dd0ceca5746f45499e4a29fc9d1f7d3c
Virtualization: vmware
Operating System: Ubuntu 20.04.3 LTS
Kernel:          Linux 5.4.0-91-generic
Architecture:   x86-64

```

Java


```
simavi@mescobrasd-app:~$ java -version
openjdk version "17.0.1" 2021-10-19
OpenJDK Runtime Environment (build 17.0.1+12-Ubuntu-120.04)
OpenJDK 64-Bit Server VM (build 17.0.1+12-Ubuntu-120.04, mixed mode,
sharing)
```

Docker

Client: Docker Engine - Community

```
Version:           20.10.11
API version:       1.41
Go version:        go1.16.9
Git commit:        dea9396
Built:             Thu Nov 18 00:37:06 2021
OS/Arch:           linux/amd64
Context:           default
Experimental:      true
```

Server: Docker Engine - Community

```
Engine:
Version:           20.10.11
API version:       1.41 (minimum version 1.12)
Go version:        go1.16.9
Git commit:        847da18
Built:             Thu Nov 18 00:35:15 2021
OS/Arch:           linux/amd64
Experimental:      false
```

containerd:

```
Version:           1.4.12
GitCommit:         7b11cfaabd73bb80907dd23182b9347b4245eb5d
```

runc:

```
Version:           1.0.2
GitCommit:         v1.0.2-0-g52b36a2
```

docker-init:

Version: 0.19.0
GitCommit: de40ad0

Python

Python 3.8.10 (default, Nov 26 2021, 20:14:08)
[GCC 9.3.0] on linux

Keycloak

Keycloak-15.0.2

Kafka (Docker container)

```
4d3001a16993 bitnami/kafka:3 "/opt/bitnami/script..." 7 weeks ago Up 7 weeks 0.0.0.0:9092->9092/tcp, :::9092->9092/tcp simavi_kafka_1
```

```
b7f71d79bcab bitnami/zookeeper:3.7 "/opt/bitnami/script..." 7 weeks ago Up 7 weeks 2888/tcp, 3888/tcp, 0.0.0.0:2181->2181/tcp, :::2181->2181/tcp, 8080/tcp simavi_zookeeper_1
```

INFO Kafka version: 3.0.0 (org.apache.kafka.common.utils.AppInfoParser)

7.3.4 EDGE PLUG-INS

Edge plug-in are components used to prepare data from different sources (patients, caregivers, clinical data, external systems data, etc), to anonymise it and to prepare for the transfer to the central system.

The approach is to have plug-in developed as part of the project and placed in the project showcase, but let them be developed by third parties, during the project or outside the time frame of the project.

This will be possible by the creation of a set of interface definitions, where the metadata is exposed, so that, each plug-in will be able to present in an understandable format, the available data.

The data exposed will be in a common format (e.g. JSON), and their interfaces will use a standard mechanism (e.g. REST API)

The implementation depends on the hosting device, and the provider.

Each plug-in will expose metadata, in a common structure, and will be discoverable by the central system.

7.3.5 CONTINUOUS INTEGRATION/CONTINUOUS DELIVERY (CI/CD)

CI/CD mechanism will use the GitHub³ cloud mechanism.

It will be based on:

- › Git Collaborative Coding (source repository),

³ <https://github.com>

- › Git Actions: GitHub Actions makes it easy to automate all your software workflows, now with world-class CI/CD. Build, test, and deploy your code right from GitHub. Make code reviews, branch management, and issue triaging work the way you want.
- › Git Packages: Host your own software packages or use them as dependencies in other projects. Both private and public hosting available.

7.3.6 SECURITY

Security will be developed around OAuth2 and OpenID specifications. The tool proposed is Keycloak⁴.

Keycloak is an open-source Identity and Access Management solution aimed at modern applications and services. It makes it easy to secure applications and services with little to no code.

Users authenticate with Keycloak rather than individual applications. This means that your applications don't have to deal with login forms, authenticating users, and storing users. Once logged-in to Keycloak, users don't have to login again to access a different application.

This also applies to logout. Keycloak provides single-sign out, which means users only have to logout once to be logged-out of all applications that use Keycloak.

Keycloak can also authenticate users with existing OpenID Connect or SAML 2.0 Identity Providers.

Keycloak has built-in support to connect to existing LDAP or Active Directory servers.

Keycloak is based on standard protocols and provides support for OpenID Connect, OAuth 2.0, and SAML.

7.4 COMMUNICATION LAYER

For this layer we are presenting the communication mechanism between the modules. We are considering synchronous and asynchronous communications. For each module we are presenting how it communicates with the others.

7.4.1 DATA SHARING

7.4.1.1 Data Ingestion Module

The MES-CoBraD Data Ingestion component is implemented through the Digital Enabler “Dataflow”, a workflow manager based on Apache Airflow (<https://airflow.apache.org>). It allows to define jobs that can be triggered both through REST APIs invocation and through jobs scheduled according to specific calendars.

On one hand, it strictly interacts with the “Local Backend” component, presented in the following section, to collect anonymised (and/or pseudo-anonymised) data from the medical centres’ intranet; on the other hand it communicates with the Data Lake, presented in section 1.1.1.1, through several connectors, in order to store the collected data into the MES-CoBraD storage layer.

Thanks to the Dataflow capabilities, the ingestion processes can be both synchronous and asynchronous. The synchronous ingestion will be triggered directly from the Local Backend to an authenticated REST API containing, in the payload, the data to be stored; on the other hand, the asynchronous ingestion will be triggered through scheduled batch processes that will be able to harvest data from the external data sources and store them in the data lake.

⁴ <https://www.keycloak.org/>

7.4.1.2 *Local back end: Edge computing scenarios*

The MES-CoBraD Project has the purpose of working with Real World Data to perform analysis and clinical research. One of the most relevant concerns, when talking about health data, is the compliance of the system with the most advanced security standards. To be sure that the clinical data won't exit from the medical centres' intranet before the anonymisation, the MES-CoBraD platform allows to deploy an edge module that will act as a "Local Backend" and that will be able to manipulate personal data for anonymisation and aggregation purposes.

The data input on the local backend will be done through direct upload from the MES-CoBraD web interface; once the data are uploaded, they will be elaborated asynchronously to create an "opaque" version of the data that are ready to be uploaded onto the cloud. After a human validation, the output of these elaborations will be pushed on the Data Ingestion Module (see section 1.2.1.1) to let it persist on the Data Lake.

7.4.1.3 *Data Harmonisation Module*

A harmonisation process can be triggered both in a synchronous and asynchronous way. The synchronous trigger is available through REST API; in this case the outcome of the invoked mashup will be returned as a response of the HTTP request.

The asynchronous triggers are available through different approaches and protocols: MQTT, Kafka and scheduled executions done according to a predefined frequency.

In all these cases the Data Mashup Editor can send the output to several so-called "Targets", using different connectors to communicate with external systems. Such targets can be databases, data lakes, brokers or any other kind of system (even legacy ones).

Within the scope of the MES-CoBraD project the DME communicates both synchronously and asynchronously with the Data Lake, depending on the most relevant flow for each kind of data. If a mashup is invoked through API, then the output of the invocation is both returned as HTTP response and stored into the data lake, if it is enabled as target. A mashup is periodically scheduled then its output is sent to all the target asynchronously.

7.4.2 SYNCHRONOUS COMMUNICATION INFO

Synchronous communication is based on REST API calls. Each module present in the application is able to expose API and also able to consume APIs exposed by other modules.

7.4.3 ASYNCHRONOUS COMMUNICATIONS

Asynchronous data communication is based on the usage of a Queue mechanism. This queue mechanism will be part of the Platform and will be based on Kafka broker.

7.5 Information Layer

For this layer we are presenting the data structures and data models used by different parts of the system. We are presenting first the data from the sources, then the main storage mechanism which is the Data Lake.

7.5.1 DATA COLLECTED

7.5.1.1 Data Ingestion Module

The Data Ingestion module will handle several kinds of data. One of the main challenges of the MES-CoBraD platform is to be able to deal with really heterogenous and scattered data sources. The collected data will be Real World Data belonging to three possible categories:

- › Single Variable Data (SVD): like timeseries and other single value data
- › Multiple Variable Data (MVD): like questionnaires
- › Complex Structured Data (CSD): like MRI, EEG and other images

For each of the up-mentioned categories, the data will come into the platform according to the guidelines mentioned in chapter 3 of the D3.1 – Project Manual and its following updates.

7.5.1.2 Data Harmonization Module

One of the main concerns of the project is to make the clinical research results as most transparent and reproducible as possible; for this reason, the data collected into the Data Lake will be subject of a harmonisation step that is a critical point of the entire RWD management lifecycle.

Such harmonisation will be done according to a pre-defined set of data models that will be agreed within the consortium during the project execution. For this purpose, the usage of standardised models and codes are a necessary and essential, then, many standards, like HL7 (<http://www.hl7.org>), the Generalized Data Model (<https://rdcu.be/cFmFI>), the FIWARE Smart Data Models (<https://www.fiware.org/developers/smart-data-models>) and the International Classification of Diseases (ICD) (<https://icd.who.int/en>) will be taken in consideration during the agreement of the target model for each data type.

7.5.2 DATA LAKE

As mentioned in previous chapters, the Data Lake is a multi-technological component. It involves several kinds of storage: object storage, relation and no-relational databases and log servers. Such a variety of technology is quite mandatory because of the heterogeneity of the input data sources.

Exactly for these reasons, the Data Lake doesn't have a specific reference data model, it is a container of several heterogenous data that may also differ a lot each-other. It will contain both files in several formats like, among others, CSV, JSON, dicom, edf and txt; for each of which it will store both the "raw" format, coming from the data source, along with the harmonised version.

7.5.3 USER MANAGEMENT AND ACCESS CONTROL

The user management and access control in MES-CoBraD is implemented through Keycloak, as described above. Such a component allows to organise the users in different ways and manage the access control according to different patterns.

In Keycloak there are 5 main entities:

- › Users: a physical person that is enabled to access the platform;
- › Groups: a collection of users that have something in common (e.g. share the same medical centre);

- › Roles: a user's part in the platform (e.g. doctor, patient, caregiver);
- › Permissions: a set of flags that define what a user can or cannot do;
- › Clients: a software system that wants to use keycloak as identity manager.

These entities are related each-other as depicted below:

Figure 16 - Identity Manager entities relations

As shown in the picture:

- a User can belong to several Groups, and a Group can encapsulate many Users;
- a Role can be associated both to many Groups and to many Users, whereas both a Group and a User can have many Roles;
- a Permission can be coupled with multiple Roles, and a single Role can be coupled with many Permissions;
- a Client can have associated multiple Roles and the same Role can be associated with multiple Clients.

The Keycloak tool contains many other concepts, like Identity Providers, Events, Scopes etc... but they are not so relevant for the purposes of the project and for this reason they are not explicitly mentioned here.

7.6 FUNCTION LAYER

For this layer we are presenting the main processes applied to data. We start by presenting the data preparation, next go to the Advanced Analytics Expert Systems and AI Adaptive training.

7.6.1 DATA PREPARATION

7.6.1.1 Data Harmonization Module

The Data Harmonisation Module is responsible to harmonise raw data that flow into the data lake from different data sources. These data can rely on different protocols, formats and standards, for this reason the goal of this component is to process such heterogenous data to allow further elaborations and data analysis with the same schema.

The Data Mashup editor allows to define data workflows by composing already defined building blocks or by defining new ones trough the UI. Such blocks (also called "Operators") enable different kind of elaborations, like quality checks, object creations, normalisation and data manipulation.

When the Data Ingestion module persists new data within the data lake, the DME gets those new data, processes them through the defined mashup and asynchronously persists the harmonised version within the data lake itself, making them ready to be processed or analysed by other components.

7.6.1.2 Data anonymization

The data anonymization is a key-point of the entire platform. This step will be executed on the “Local backend” through the most advanced technologies available.

The data upload will be possible through the web UI of the MES-CoBraD platform; differently from the most frequent client-server pattern, they won’t be uploaded directly on the cloud, but will be sent on the local backend documented in section 1.2.1.2 for pre-elaboration and anonymisation purposes.

Anonymisation framework like ARX (<https://doi.org/10.1002/spe.2812>) will support personal data removal.

After this automatic and asynchronous process, the data will be labelled as “Unloadable” and will move to a human validation step. The Scientist that originally uploaded the data will review the “opaque” version created by the component, in order to be sure that no personal data has been left unchanged. Then will explicitly approve the upload on the cloud that will happen immediately after the approval.

7.6.2 QUERY BUILDER

The Query Builder serves as a connecting role in the MES-CoBraD ecosystem, being able to retrieve and appropriately process data before forwarding them to other components. It will also be capable of creating new datasets.

Figure 17 Query Builder Interface Diagram

Interface Specifications

The interfaces specified are referring to the conceptual communication between the components. The actual technical implementation, transfer of data and coordination of actions is done mostly through the workflow manager of the expert system. The interfaces applicable to the Query Builder component, as depicted in Figure 17 above are:

> QB.I.01: Data Lake Interface Retrieving Data

This interface allows the Query Builder component to retrieve datasets from the Data Lake for further processing.

- **Input:** Datasets;
- **Output:** Not applicable.

› **QB.I.02: Data Lake Interface Saving New Dataset**

This interface allows the Query Builder component to save the results of the dataset processing in order to create a new dataset.

- **Input:** Not applicable;
- **Output:** New dataset.

› **QB.I.03: Task Manager**

This interface allows the Query Builder component to send metadata of a dataset needed by the Task Manager to be used in a step in the BPMN builder.

- **Input:** : Task Manager request;
- **Output:** Dataset configuration data.

› **QB.I.04: Workflow Manager**

This interface allows the Query Builder component to send datasets specified by the metadata during an instance of the BPMN to be further used in other components.

- **Input:** : Dataset configuration data;
- **Output:** Datasets.

› **QB.I.05: Visualisation Interface**

This interface allows the Query Builder component to send datasets to the Visualisation component to display them to the user.

- **Input:** Not applicable;
- **Output:** Datasets.

› **QB.I.06: AI - ML Interface**

This interface allows the Query Builder component to send datasets for further use in model training or general configuration.

- **Input:** Not applicable;
- **Output:** Datasets.

› **QB.I.07: Advanced Analytics Interface**

This interface allows the Query Builder component to send datasets for further use in data analytics.

- **Input:** Not applicable;
- **Output:** Datasets.

› **QB.I.08: User Access Control System Interface**

This interface allows the Query Builder component to verify the identity of the user and whether they have access to the information they aim to query.

- **Input:** Not applicable;
- **Output:** Keycloak tool metadata.

Figure 18 Query Builder Modules

Query Builder Modules

The Query Builder will be developed using the FastAPI (Python-based Framework). This component will provide endpoints for the creation as well as the execution of SQL queries. The modules that formulate the Query Builder are depicted in Figure 18. The Query Builder will receive GET HTTP Requests, in which there will be parameters that will define the desired SQL query in JSON format. The body of the request will include information about the table name, the selected column names, the aggregation functions, the limit, etc. The Query Builder will support all the basic SQL commands, such as SELECT, GROUP BY, ORDER BY, JOIN and all the aggregation functions (SUM, AVG, MAX, MIN, COUNT). Given the input, the Query Builder will construct the desired SQL query.

Afterwards, the Query Executor will communicate with the Data Lake and will execute the SQL query in order to retrieve/get the wanted data. As a final step, the Query Executor will return the extracted data to the component that made the request.

7.6.3 ADVANCED ANALYTICS

The Advanced Analytics module will be used to implement statistical data analysis and hypothesis testing, analysis of time-series data, and Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) image analysis. This multi-purpose analytics service will provide the end-users (scientists - clinicians) the ability to analyse patients' data, develop insights about patients' health conditions and implement scientific research formulating hypotheses.

Figure 19 Advanced Analytics Interface Diagram

Interface Specifications

The interfaces specified are referring to the conceptual communication between the components. The actual technical implementation, transfer of data and coordination of actions is done mostly through the workflow manager of the expert system. The interfaces applicable to the Advanced Analytics component, as also depicted in Figure 19, are:

> AA.I.01: Data Lake Interface

This interface allows the Advanced Analytics component to save the results of the analytics process in order to create a new dataset.

- **Input:** Not applicable;
- **Output:** Analytics results.

> AA.I.02: Task Manager

This interface allows the Advanced Analytics component to send metadata needed by the Task Manager to specify the details of a single step in the BPMN builder.

- **Input:** Task Manager request;
- **Output:** Analysis configuration data.

> AA.I.03: Workflow Manager

This interface allows the Advanced Analytics component to receive the metadata necessary to execute an action, as specified in the Task Manager. After the completion of the action, the results of the analysis along with any relevant metadata are returned to the Workflow Manager.

- **Input:** : Analysis configuration data ;
- **Output:** Analytics results.

> AA.I.04: Visualisation Interface

This interface allows the Advanced Analytics component to send the results of the analytics process, to the Visualisation component in the appropriate format, so they can be presented to the user.

- **Input:** Not applicable;

- **Output:** Analytics results.

› **AA.I.05: AI - ML Interface**

This interface allows the Advanced Analytics component to transfer the resulting data of the analytics process to the AI – ML component for further use in model training or general configuration.

- **Input:** Not applicable;
- **Output:** Analytics results.

› **AA.I.06: Query Builder Interface**

This interface allows the Advanced Analytics component to receive datasets from the Query Builder, either datasets already existing in the Data Lake or produced by the user inside the Query Builder.

- **Input:** Query builder dataset;
- **Output:** Not applicable.

› **AA.I.07: User Access Control System Interface**

This interface allows the Advanced Analytics component to verify the identity, role and access rights of the user that uses the module.

- **Input:** Not applicable;
- **Output:** Keycloak tool metadata.

Figure 20 Advanced Analytics Modules

Advanced Analytics will be implemented in FastAPI. FastAPI is a modern and fast (high-performance) web framework for building APIs with Python 3.6+. The modules that formulate the Advanced Analytics component and its functionalities are depicted in Figure 20 and analysed below.

Statistical Analysis

The Advanced Analytics module will contain a series of statistical packages, which include functions that can be used in the analysis process. The focus of this component will be to provide interpretability of the data. For this purpose, methods for investigating the data, analysing the relationship between variables (e.g., correlation, regression algorithms) and processing datasets for identifying individual data points associations (e.g., clustering techniques) will be applied. A series of descriptive analytical tools, in terms of describing and examining statistical characteristics of the data samples, will be available from various packages and libraries such as NumPy, SciPy, Pandas, Scikit-learn, statsmodels, Pingouin.

Hypothesis Testing

A specific Hypothesis Testing module will be created as part of the Advanced Analytics component development. This module will serve the requirements of clinical researchers to examine their research questions and investigate statistical differences in patients' sample data. The end-users will be able to formulate their hypotheses and evaluate them, using several statistical tests, proving if they can be accepted or not. Based on the assumptions and the purpose of each statistical test, several parametric (e.g., t-test, ANOVA, z-test) and non-parametric (e.g., Chi-squared test, Mann-Whitney U test, Wilcoxon signed-rank test) methods will be employed. Also, methods to adjust the p-values for multiple comparisons will be provided. The Hypothesis testing module is powered by the Advanced Analytics module using most of its tools and capabilities.

Time series pre-processing

In addition, the Advanced Analytics module will provide algorithms for processing time series data, i.e., electroencephalogram (EEG), polysomnography (PSG) data, etc. Depending on the format of the data, the *MNE* library in Python could be used for having access to the data. Specifically, this library provides functions for reading EDF or EDF+ files. Options for applying filters, i.e., bandpass, highpass, lowpass, etc. will be provided and could be implemented via the library *SciPy* in Python. Also, some methods for repairing artefacts, which are implemented in the *MNE* library could be provided.

Time series analysis

When it comes to the analysis, time-series analysis and forecasting methods will be provided. Autoregressive moving average model (ARMA) constitutes an example, which is implemented via the library named *statsmodels* in Python. Also, spectral analysis via Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT), Discrete Wavelet Decomposition (DWT), etc. are necessary and implemented in most open-source libraries. The Advanced Analytics component will also provide algorithms for actigraphy data analysis, including the detection of rest periods, the implementation of advanced signal processing functions, and many more.

MRI pre-processing

The Advanced Analytics component will provide algorithms for processing MRI data. In case images are in *dicom* format, the component will enable the conversion into *nifty* files if necessary, since this format is used by most libraries/tools. Through the component, pre-processing steps can be applied to MRI data through this component, including realignment, slice time correction, un-distortion, co-registration, normalisation, smoothing, etc.

MRI Analysis

The general linear model (GLM) can be implemented through the Advanced Analytics component. The

GLM is used for making inferences about brain responses in a single subject. Also, the GLM can be used for making inferences about the group (second-level or group analysis). All these algorithms could be used via the library *nipype*, which provides interfaces to most neuroimaging tools, including FSL, ANTs and SPM.

When performing an analysis, it will be possible to select the cases in which the analysis will be performed, based on some inclusion and exclusion criteria. Following the completion of an analysis, the module will be able to generate a detailed report on it, which will include a variety of information on how the analysis was performed (e.g., the method that was used, the version of the programming language, the version of the pipeline/package).

7.6.4 DATA AND RESULTS VISUALISATION

The Query Builder serves as a connecting role in the MES-CoBraD ecosystem, being able to retrieve and appropriately process data before forwarding them to other components. It will also be capable of creating new datasets.

Figure 21 Visualisation and Results Interface Diagram

Interface Specifications

The interfaces specified are referring to the conceptual communication between the components. The actual technical implementation, transfer of data and coordination of actions is done mostly through the workflow manager of the expert system. The interfaces applicable to the Data and Results Visualisation component, as depicted in Figure 22 below, are:

> V.I.01: Task Manager

This interface allows the Data and Results Visualisation component to send metadata of visualisations needed by the Task Manager to be used in a step in the BPMN builder.

- **Input:** Task Manager request;
- **Output:** Visualisation configuration data.

> V.I.02: Workflow Manager

This interface allows the Data and Results Visualisation component to send visualisations to be displayed

during an instance of a BPM step.

- **Input:** : Visualisation configuration data.
- **Output:** Visualisations.

> V.I.03: Query Builder Interface

This interface allows the Data and Results Visualisation component to receive data (as the result of a query), directly from the query builder which in turn is displayed to the user.

- **Input:** Dataset;
- **Output:** Not applicable.

> V.I.04: AI - ML Interface

This interface allows the Data and Results Visualisation component to save the results of the AI- ML component so they can be displayed to the user.

- **Input:** AI- ML results;
- **Output:** Not applicable.

> V.I.05: Advanced Analytics Interface

This interface allows the Data and Results Visualisation component to save the results of the analytics process so they can be displayed to the user.

- **Input:** Analytics results;
- **Output:** Not applicable.

> V.I.06: User Access Control System Interface

This interface allows the Data and Results Visualisation component to verify the identity of the user accessing the information.

- **Input:** Not applicable;
- **Output:** Keycloak tool metadata.

Figure 22 Data and Results Visualisation Modules

Visualisation Modules

The Data and Results Visualisation module will be implemented using the FastAPI framework. The modules that formulate the Data and Results Visualisation component and its functionalities are depicted in Figure 22. The resulting incoming data from the components we mentioned previously, will be available

as a dashlet that the user can insert into a customisable dashboard. The workflow will let the user choose the type of visualisation (simple chart of values, barchart, lineplot, etc) and the settings that will be used for this visualisation (range, axes, etc). Then, there will be an option to add the visualisation to the dashboard where the user can do various other actions (change titles, rearrange dashlets, etc) and another option for saving the visualisation.

AmCharts (JavaScript-based library) will be used for the needs of more general visualisations (e.g. time-series data). It is especially useful as it offers a wide variety of visualisations and provides interactivity out of the box.

Various Python libraries will be used for visualising scientific data (EEG, MEG, MRI, etc) and offer statistical analysis visualisations. Some examples of these libraries are Nilearn, Visbrain and MNE-Python.

7.6.5 EXPERT SYSTEM

Expert System is a set of tools that provide the ability for the end user to execute dynamically created processes and create potentially unlimited workflows.

The Expert System will be executed on a closed dockerized environment (i.e. uses the Docker container platform – ref: <https://www.docker.com/>), uses the python programming language (ref: <https://www.python.org/>) and the Django web framework (ref: <https://www.djangoproject.com/>).

The Expert system will, also, integrate the following tools which have been reviewed, tested, and qualified so far:

- › SpiffWorkflow, an open-source python package managing workflows.
(Ref: <https://github.com/sartography/SpiffWorkflow>)
- › BPMN.io, an open source javascript package used to design BPMN diagrams.
(Ref: <https://bpmn.io/toolkit/bpmn-js/>)

All data exchanges between functions and features will be JSON compliant.

7.6.5.1 Task Manager

Figure 23 – Task Manager

Task is the ability of the user to create, update and delete data collected and used in an active workflow. A task can be a data manipulation form, a third-party application, or an AI algorithm service.

This function provides different features, such as:

Task Creation

A user can create tasks and the corresponding integration “drivers”. Each task has a predefined structured input received by the previous or the initial step and produces an explicitly defined output for exchange with the following one.

As mentioned previously, each task will represent a specific function that will be executed when the workflow gets at that stage and all the available functions will be available for the user to select.

- › If the task executes an AI algorithmic process, then the corresponding Artificial Intelligence module (ref: chapter 5.5.5 Artificial Intelligence) is solely responsible for parsing the data and executes the algorithm.
- › If the task executes an API integration, then the call is made given the data input and the output is parsed to be harmonized.
- › The task executes a form or a data manipulation “engine”.

Task View

The user can list all the available above-mentioned tasks, with filters.

Task Update

The user can update all the available above-mentioned tasks, as in “Task Creation”.

Task Delete

The user can delete all, or a specific task from the available list.

7.6.5.2 Workflow Manager

Figure 24 – Workflow Manager

Workflow Manager is the function that handles all workflow related features.

Workflow is a set of tasks that may follow the Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN) specification and provides the end users the capability of executing any process that follows or resembles a protocol streamlines their work.

This function provides different features, such as:

UI Process Designer

UI Process Designer is a Graphical User Interface exposed on web that creates workflows with simple interactive tools. Each user will be able to design on a canvas a workflow, match it with tasks and operators to capture their work's core logic. The user can select tasks and pre-defined functions, manipulate and parametrize the data, to get the desired result.

Process Executor

The Process Executor is a function tightly connected with a user interface and a backend service that handles the connection between the user and the work process. The created BPMN, or Non-BPMN workflow can be initiated by the user and each task is executed using the logic operators. As in the task creation, depending on the type, the input data are parsed and transferred to the corresponding execution function and then the function itself is placed in a queue that waits for a result. Then, if the response is successful, then the function checks for next steps and if it is unsuccessful, then the process stops, or checks for fail-safe alternative tasks.

Task Optimizer

This function is responsible for controlling the metadata of previous and next executed tasks and collect timeseries data that makes statistical analysis on each task and optimize its performance. It will, also, be connected to the therapeutic / diagnostic guideline and rule system to assist and generate next-task recommendations.

Process Optimizer

This function is responsible for controlling the metadata of executed workflows and collect timeseries data that makes statistical analysis on each task and optimize its performance (accuracy, timings, status, etc.). It will, also, be connected to the therapeutic / diagnostic guideline and rule system to assist and generate workflow recommendations. These recommendations can be used in a later stage to update existing workflow paths or help a user to make better decisions.

7.6.6 ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

The Artificial Intelligence System is an autonomous service which consists of a series of sub-system services for providing data analysis. Analyses the input data, checks for execution options and finally executes the desired algorithm.

The AI System will be executed on a closed dockerised environment (i.e. uses the Docker container platform – ref: <https://www.docker.com/>), uses the python programming language (ref: <https://www.python.org/>) and the open-source Django python package (ref: <https://www.djangoproject.com/>).

The Artificial Intelligence system will, also, integrate the following tools which have been reviewed and qualified so far:

- › TensorFlow (ref: <https://www.tensorflow.org/>)
- › PyTorch (ref: <https://pytorch.org/>)
- › Keras (ref: <https://keras.io/>)
- › Alibi Explain (ref: <https://www.seldon.io/tech/products/alibi/>)
- › Captum (ref: <https://captum.ai/>)

All data exchanges between functions and features will be JSON compliant.

7.6.6.1 Analyse data

Figure 25 – Analyse data

This function, the input data is analysed by type and separated based on Single Variable Data (SVD), Multi Variable Data (MVD) and Complex Structured Data (CSD).

This separation is suitable for the logical course that the system will follow in the selection of algorithm, plus

7.6.6.2 Parse options

Figure 26 – Data parsing

This function checks any parameters given during input initialization. The parameters will be specified and will delimit the available solutions when selecting an algorithm.

Such parameters will be speed / accuracy, prediction / diagnosis / treatment, explainable true / false, a specific algorithm, etc, and they will be optional.

7.6.6.3 Algorithm selection and execution

Figure 27 – Algorithm selection and execution

In case no algorithm default is given, then it will check the input parameters, and will supply the appropriate algorithm with the data (see Algorithm as a Service).

7.6.6.4 Algorithm as a Service

In this function, all available algorithms are standardized to run under a common ecosystem, or a set of services that will host different algorithms, prepare the data to be in a form recognizable by them, and finally collect the information so that to transfer it to the next stage.

Each service will be compliant to REST API practices and will use a queuing mechanism (such as MQTT).

7.6.6.5 Questionnaire Builder

The questionnaire builder will be exposed on portal as a WEB application. It will developed on top of a web server (Wildfly or Tomcat), following the requirements specified in chapter 4.3.15 of the present document. The questionnaire builder will be developed on top of Django, and use django-form-builder ⁵

⁵ <https://pypi.org/project/django-form-builder/>

7.7 BUSINESS LAYER

This layer focuses on the business value of the system as understood by the final users.

7.7.1 PRESENTATION

The platform will consist of a series of services that will be interconnected in such a way as to be easy to handle by scientists, patients, and medical staff. When the user enters the home page of the application, the user should provide his login credentials, and proceed to the services that will be available and mapped to his specific role. For example, a clinician that supervises the questionnaire process, enters the required data, the patient information that he is going to enter for processing (e.g., age), but also the additional information necessary for the analysis models. After completing the above step and following the anonymization step, the data will be sent from the edge backend to the main platform. After processing the data from a series of steps, the user will be able to use the system by selecting a feature from a wide set of tools, algorithms, as well as creating a custom business logic using the UI designer. Finally, by using these tools, mistakes are avoided, processes are accelerated, waiting is reduced, and each phase of the project is standardized with clear procedures that are distinguished by everyone.

All users are required to login to the platform, logout, change their profile data and delete their account to remove all data. After the user has logged into the system, the system checks for the user role and depending on that, a different set of actions can be performed, as described below.

7.7.1.1 System Admin

Data Collection

- › When it comes to data collection about our patients, primary data is also typically first-party data. First-party data is the information you gather directly from our audience. It could include data you gathered from online properties, data in our patient's relationship management system or non-online data you collect from our patients through surveys and various other sources. Because first-party data comes directly from the patients, you can have high confidence in its accuracy, as well as its relevance to the system. The configuration phase is crucial because it turns raw data into valuable insights that we can use to enhance our data management strategy, system integration and application decisions.
- › CRUD stands for create, read, update, and delete. Those are the basic operations that you can perform in a modern DB system. But there's always more to business applications than that. Business logic or domain logic is that part of the program which encodes the real-world business rules that determine how data can be created, stored, and changed. It prescribes how business objects interact with one another and enforces the routes and the methods by which business objects are accessed and updated. Business Rules describe the operations, definitions and constraints that apply to an organization. The operations collectively form a process; every business uses these processes to form systems that get things done.
- › Track logs of each mashup execution and the status of each step of the data flow. The types of information and format of messages found in an application log file will vary by application. This is because these variables aren't determined by external guidelines or by the operating system.

Data Harmonization

- › A basic configuration and harmonization process should optimize the data, to achieve less time, less effort and less resources spent for the given action. Extract, transform, and load

are three database operations responsible for moving your data into a common database. Extraction reads the data in the original database, transformation changes the format so it's ready for querying and analysis, while loading writes the data to your destination database. Traditionally, this can be the most issue-prone part of data integration because an error in one step causes inaccurate or missing data throughout. Data normalization and harmonization can be used interchangeably. Both imply making the fundamental aspects of your data all the same.

- › Organizations that keep track of patients' data, accounts, other information, health data, and other records require data storage hardware and applications that provide persistent storage. This data is typically organized into a database, which is simply an organized collection of data that may be viewed electronically. There are many types of databases: hierarchical databases, graph databases, and object-oriented databases to name a few. The most implemented type of database is a relational database, which consists of data tabled in rows and columns and connected to other tables with complementary information by a system of keywords that includes primary keys and foreign keys.
- › Track logs of each mashup execution could give analytics and statistics for every step taken, for further optimization of the algorithmic tree. Define which are the possible triggers for a mashup. A mashup is a technique by which a website or Web application uses data, presentation, or functionality from two or more sources to create a new service. Mashups are made possible via Web services or public APIs that (generally) allow free access. Most mashups are visual and interactive in nature. To a user, a mashup should provide a richer, more interactive experience. A mashup is also beneficial to developers because it requires less code, allowing for a quicker development cycle and finally, define where the mashup result will be published

Data Lake

- › A data lake is a central storage repository that holds big data from many sources in a raw, granular format. It can store structured, semi-structured, or unstructured data, which means data can be kept in a more flexible format for future use. When storing data, a data lake associates it with identifiers and metadata tags for faster retrieval. Data lakes are usually configured on a cluster of inexpensive and scalable commodity hardware. This allows data to be dumped in the lake in case there is a need for it later without having to worry about storage capacity. The clusters could either exist on-premises or in the cloud.
- › Data lakes, with their ability to handle velocity and variety, have business intelligence users excited. Now, there is an opportunity to combine processed data with subjective data available on the internet. It is possible to sift through machine data such as X-rays and MRI scans to determine causal patterns of diseases. In IoT applications, a huge amount of sensor data can be processed with incredible speeds. Data lakes are not only useful in advanced predictive analytical applications, but also in regular organizational reporting, especially when it involves different data formats. Last, a common path using CRUD for RWD files should be used.
- › The user management and access control in MES-CoBraD is implemented through a well-known identity manager named Keycloak. Such a component allows to organise the users in different ways and manage the access control according to different patterns.

In Keycloak there are 5 main entities:

- Users: a physical person that is enabled to access the platform.
- Groups: a collection of users that have something in common (e.g., share the same medical centre).
- Roles: a user's part in the platform (e.g., doctor, patient, caregiver).
- Permissions: a set of flags that define what a user can or cannot do.
- Clients: a software system that wants to use keycloak as identity manager.

› The above structure, can give the feature to:

- create and delete a user
- Suspend a user account
- Create, read, update, and delete a user group
- Associate a user with a group
- Create, read, update, and delete a user role
- Associate a user role with in-platform permissions
- Associate a user role with a user

7.7.1.2 *Scientist Coordinator*

As a scientist coordinator, the user can collect patient and other data from the edge computing modules and configure the information upon send to the main platform. During the harmonization process, the user will be able to view and configure the process itself. The user can also create, read, update, and delete mashups, track logs about their execution, define the possible triggers that might exist, or the destination of a published result and finally create, read, update, and delete a data source that can be used with them.

7.7.1.3 *Scientist*

As a scientist, the user can complete, edit, and evaluate questionnaires and send/register them on the platform. After the collection of this information, the user will be able to create, read, update, and delete mashups, track logs about their execution, define the possible triggers that might exist, or the destination of a published result and finally create, read, update, and delete a data source that can be used with them. One key feature is that the Edge platform can provide an on-site anonymization tool that the user can exploit and edit the raw data before uploading to the system. Furthermore, the variables used within the platform, can be managed, and used as research protocol and the user can develop new latent variables from other user defined variables.

When the data are ready to be processed, the user is transferred to the Expert System and the Data analytics modules. On the Expert System, the user can create, read, update, and delete workflows i.e., flow of actions that reflect a protocol, including timelines and processes. The user can use simple and complex variables and select relations of priority and posteriority between steps in processes in a flexible manner. Furthermore, the system can inform the user about the posterior probabilities of the proposed next step during the execution of the workflows, but also make recommendations and give the ability for the user to select the next step. The user can provide feedback from patients and clinicians, to help optimizing the process and the accuracy of the system and can introduce diagnostic and therapeutic guideline libraries for being referenced against the Expert System in making possible diagnoses.

In the phase of analysis and hypothesis testing, the user can select functions from statistical packages and cases based on inclusion and exclusion of criteria to analyse simple or complex data and generate reports. The complex data, like images, MRIs etc., will be analysed by open-source modules that can be integrated by the user. All the analyses will be visualized on dashboards where the user can create SQL queries by providing JSON formatted data to display time series data analyses, then view the results and aggregate part of the data and highlight part of graphs or timeseries to be labelled.

Last but not least, the user will be able to share and exploit artificial intelligence algorithms and datasets, and share the derived analyses from collected, acquired, linked, and integrated data among stakeholders.

7.7.1.4 *Clinician*

As a scientist, the user can complete, edit and evaluate questionnaires and send/register them on the platform. After the collection of this information, the user will be able to alter the data if any missing value is noticed. One key feature is that the Edge platform can provide an onsite anonymization tool that the user can exploit and edit the raw data before uploading to the system. Furthermore, the variables used within the platform, can be managed, and used as research protocol and the user can develop new latent variables from other user defined variables.

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7.7.1.5 *Caregiver*

As a caregiver, the user can be informed by the Expert System on the next recommended diagnostic step, so as depending on the data available to the Expert System at any given time, it can start forming hypotheses based on the "chief complaint" and "deep-phenotype" of a patient and instruct on accessing missing variables. Can, also, complete questionnaires and send/register them on the platform.

7.7.1.6 *Patient*

A patient, after signing in the platform, can complete questionnaires and send/register them on the platform, configure their data that are being collected and provide feedback to users on the meaning of the data they have entered. Finally, they can be informed by the Expert System on the next recommended

diagnostic step, so as depending on the data available to the Expert System at any given time, it can start forming hypotheses based on the "chief complaint" and "deep-phenotype" of a patient and instruct on accessing missing variables.

7.7.2 BUSINESS VALUE

The growth of AI and expert systems in the healthcare market is majorly driven by increase of volume of healthcare data and rise in complexities of datasets. Data acquisition and presentation, interoperability, record keeping and access, communication and integration of information, surveillance, information storage and retrieval, data analysis, decision support, and education are aspects that increase the economic and business potential of AI and expert systems in medical applications

The major drivers for the market are the increasingly large and complex datasets driving the need for AI, surging demand to reduce the increasing healthcare costs, improving computing power and declining hardware costs, a growing number of cross-industry partnerships and collaborations, and rising imbalance between health workforce and patients driving the need for improvised healthcare services. Additionally, the rising adoption of healthcare artificial intelligence in research areas, increasing range of future applications, advancements in big data analytics, potential to increase quality of care delivery play an important role in the market uptake and added value.

Critical challenges facing the AI in healthcare market include the lack of curated healthcare data, the reluctance among medical practitioners to adopt AI-based technologies concerns related to data privacy, and the lack of interoperability among AI solutions.

AI technologies possess data mining and pattern recognition capabilities that enable the prediction, diagnosis, and treatment. The healthcare ecosystem is realising the importance of AI-powered tools in the next-generation healthcare technology. It is believed that AI can bring improvements to any process within healthcare operation and delivery. For instance, the cost savings that AI can bring to the healthcare system is an important driver for implementation of AI applications. It is estimated that AI applications can cut annual US healthcare costs by USD 150 billion in 2026. A large part of these cost reductions stem from changing the healthcare model from a reactive to a proactive approach, focusing on health management rather than disease treatment. AI-based technology will have an important role in helping people stay healthy via continuous monitoring and coaching and will ensure earlier diagnosis, tailored treatments, and more efficient follow-ups.

8 CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable (D7.1) presents the MES-CoBrad System requirements and Platform Architecture specification. It is based on the developed scenarios in the eHealth ecosystem.

The deliverable is targeted for the analysts, developers and testers of the MES-CoBrad System and it be used as a reference document when developing software modules, integrate them and test the system.

It is also created to be used by the end users to understand the requirements filtered and implemented in the system, as also the architecture of the whole system.

The requirements reflect the cooperation of all the partners of the project, during several iterative meetings, where the requirements were filtered, precisely defined, and mapped to the right system components.

The requirements were grouped into sets of **functional requirements** and **non-functional requirements**. Next, the requirements were mapped to components developed by the technology providers and are characterised in terms of technological maturity, available technical solutions, and implementation risks.

Finally, the proposed components are placed in the whole architecture of the system, which will conclude the deliverable.

The architecture of MES-CoBraD platform was created facilitate interoperability and to allow for extensibility, while preserving a considerable degree of implementation-platform-independence.

The architecture is presented in two aspects: View Model and Detailed Layered model.

First a view model is used, where the following views were presented:

- > Use case view;
- > Logical View;
- > Development View;
- > Information View;
- > Deployment view;
- > Security view;
- > Integration view.

Second, the detailed layered architecture is presented, by describing:

- > Component Layer;
- > Communication Layer;
- > Information Layer;
- > Function Layer;
- > Business Layer.

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